

School Choices in the Sunflower State:

The Kansas Tax Credit Scholarship for Low Income Students Program

By Jon K.H. Davies

Overview

In many of the nation's and in Kansas' metropolitan areas schools are unequal in terms of resources and student outcomes. Throughout the country's metropolitan areas, including the Kansas City¹, Topeka, and Wichita metropolitan areas suburban school districts tend to be better resourced, and student success rates tend to be high compared to school districts.² These conditions are not an accident of nature.³ The current inequitable conditions within the different states' public-school systems is the result of long histories of discriminatory and inequitable school policies.⁴ Recently, school choice programs have been proposed as an effective means to overcome these inequities in the public school system.⁵ In Kansas, school choice has taken the form of a "Tax Credit Scholarship" program.⁶ The stated purpose of the program is to increase educational opportunities for low-income students in low-performing school districts, and therefore address the inequities within the public school system.⁷ However, the Kansas school choice laws are not good policy if the goal is to address the major inequities in the Public School System.⁸ Instead, the program likely results in further inequities.⁹

In general, it is not clear how effective school choice policies will be in contributing to improved student outcomes or equality of educational opportunity¹⁰. Indeed, school choice reforms may contribute to the persistence of the educational achievement gap between students in suburban, relatively high-income and White communities and students in urban, lower-income school districts that serve areas with relatively high minority populations.¹¹ In fact, school choice policies may allow for the structural inequities that lead to the achievement gap to be ignored, as the burden of failure is shifted from the community to the family and individual.¹² Market-like reforms should not be applied to public education. The Public-school systems of the country are arguably the most important of our public institutions, and that they provide one of the most important public goods necessary for a successful Republic. If the public-school system is broken, then the public-school system needs to be fixed.

Part I of this article looks at the history of state and school district policies resulting in inequality in the public-school system of Kansas. Part II discusses tax credit scholarship programs in general and the Kansas Tax Credit Scholarship for Low Income Students Program in particular. Part III provides an analysis of the likely and possible effects of the Kansas program. Part IV briefly discusses the merits of market fundamentalism in the contemporary school policy debates and provides alternative policies that may be more effective at increasing equality of educational opportunity in Kansas. Part V contains a brief conclusion.

¹ See Sam Dillon, *Large Urban-Suburban Gap Seen in Graduation Rates*, N.Y. TIMES, APRIL 2, 2009; *infra* n. XX.

² See *infra* pp. 5—10.

³ See *infra* pp. 3—10.

⁴ *Id.*

⁵ See *infra* pp. 11-17.

⁶ Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-4351 to -4357 (West).

⁷ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4353.

⁸ See *infra* pp. 22—34.

⁹ *Id.*

¹⁰ See James *infra* n. 168.

¹¹ *Id.*

¹² *Id.*

Table of Contents

Part I: A Brief History of Inequality in Educational Opportunity in Kansas.....3

Part II: Tax Credit Scholarship Programs and the Kansas Program.....10

A. Introduction to Tax Credit Scholarship Programs.....11

B. Introduction to the Kansas Program.....18

Part III: Analysis of the Kansas Program.....22

A. Diminishes Democratic Control.....22

B. Benefits Middle and High-Income Students.....26

C. Benefits Only Certain Social Groups.....28

Part IV: Policy Alternatives.....34

A. A Reformed Program?.....34

B. Other Forms of School Choice?.....35

C. Improve the *Public* School System.....36

Part V: Conclusion.....38

Appendix.....39

A. Illinois.....39

B. Montana.....42

C. Nevada.....46

D. South Dakota.....49

I. A Brief History of Inequality of Educational opportunity in Kansas

Like many of its sister states, Kansas schools were segregated for much of the 19th and 20th Centuries.¹³ During the state's first legislative session, a law was passed that allowed for racial segregation in common schools.¹⁴ A year later, a law allowing for segregation that was specific to city school districts was passed.¹⁵ At first, the law for city school districts was applicable only to the city school district of Leavenworth.¹⁶ In 1865, the law applicable to cities was amended to allow cities of less than 3,000 to segregate, apparently to allow for Topeka, and perhaps other cities, to establish segregated schools in their city school districts.¹⁷ In 1867, some protection was afforded to Black students through a law that fined school board members if they denied entry into a common school to any student.¹⁸ Additionally, during much of the 1870's, statutes were passed

¹³ See e.g. Hon. Gerald W. Heaney, *Busing, Timetables, Goals, and Ratios: Touchstones of Equal Opportunity*, 69 Minn. L. Rev. 735, at n. 110 (1985)(discussing school segregation laws in effect in 1900 and noting that 19 of 37 states with school segregation laws mandated the operation of separate schools for Black and White children); Davison M. Douglas, *The Limits of Law in Accomplishing Racial Change: School Segregation in the Pre-Brown North*, 44 UCLA L. Rev. 677, 682 (1997)(noting that even in states where statutes were enacted to prohibit segregation "many local school districts operated segregated schools in open defiance of state law until the early 1950's").

¹⁴ Ch. 76, 1861 Kan. Sess. Laws 261 (legislation granting school district residents consisting of the qualified electors and white female persons over the age of 21 not subject to statutory disqualification the power to vote for the creation of "separate" but "equal" schools for white and "colored" children (repealed 1874)).

¹⁵ Ch. 46, 1862 Kan. Sess. Laws 384 (requiring cities of at least 7,000 people to appropriate all taxes collected from "black or mulatto" persons for school purposes be applied to funding of separate schools for their children (amended 1864)); See Ch. 47, 1864 Kan. Sess. Laws 117 (amending the 1862 to permit rather than mandate separate schools in incorporated cities (repealed 1957)). In 1867 the law governing the incorporation of cities was reworked, to allow for cities to incorporate either as cities of the first class or of the second class, depending on population. See Ch. 19, 1867, Kan. Sess. Laws, 134 (stating that cities can incorporate as a city of the first class if the population is greater than 15,000); Ch. 69, 1867, Kan. Sess. Laws, XXX (allowing for cities with a population between 1,000 and 15,000 to incorporate as cities of the second class). At the time, the establishment of separate schools was permitted in both types of incorporated cities. See *Id.*

¹⁶ Leavenworth was the only city in Kansas with a population sufficient for incorporation under the act. See U.S. Census (1860).

¹⁷ See Ch. 47, 1865 Kan. Sess. Laws 108. The bill was introduced by S.D. Macdonald of Topeka. See HOUSE JOURNAL OF THE LEGISLATIVE ASSEMBLY OF THE STATE OF KANSAS AT ITS FOURTH SESSION, 275 (1865); THE LAWS OF THE STATE OF KANSAS PASSED AT THE FIFTH SESSION OF THE LEGISLATURE, 9 (1865). In 1865 Topeka schools were segregated when Black and White children began to be educated on separate floors in the school building they shared. See Thomas C Cox, *BLACKS IN TOPEKA KANSAS, 1865-1915: A SOCIAL HISTORY*, 27 (1991). Topeka's population in 1865 was 1,310. *Id.* at 201.

¹⁸ Ch. 125, 1867 Kan. Sess. Laws 211 (prohibiting district boards from refusing the admit any child into the common schools and fining district boards that refuse admission to a child).

restricting the ability of schools districts to establish separate schools.¹⁹ In 1876, the school laws were re-written, removing all authority for any type of school district to establish or maintain segregated schools.²⁰ However, in 1879 a statute allowing for segregation in cities of the first class was passed.²¹ A version of this law would stay on the books until 1957.²²

Although segregation was allowed in the elementary schools of cities of the first class, segregation in other types of schools was prohibited.²³ However, schools were often segregated in even where segregation was not legally permissible.²⁴ Sometimes, impermissible segregation was

¹⁹ See e.g. Ch. 65, 1873 Kan. Sess. Laws 130 (providing no provisions for the establishment of segregated schools in cities of the second class); Ch. 49, 1874 Kan. Sess. Laws 82 (making it a misdemeanor to make a “distinction on account of race, color, or previous condition of servitude” in any state “school of public instruction”); Act to Provide for the Protection of Citizens in Their Civil Rights, Ch. 49, 1874 Kan. Sess. Laws 83 (“repealing all acts or parts of acts inconsistent” with the 1874 Act to Provide for the Protection of Citizens in Their Civil and Public Rights).

²⁰ See Ch. 122, 1876 Kan. Sess. Laws 263 (providing no provisions allowing for the establishment of segregated schools in cities of the first class); Ch. 122, 1876 Kan. Sess. Laws 269 (providing no provisions allowing for the establishment of segregated schools in cities of the second class); Ch. 122, 1876 Kan. Sess. Laws 275 (providing no provisions for the establishment of segregated schools in cities of the second class); Ch. 122, 1876 Kan. Sess. Laws 256 (providing no provisions allowing for the establishment of segregated schools in common school districts). See also *Reynolds v. Bd. of Educ. of City of Topeka*, 72 P. 274, 276 (Kan. 1903)(noting that the during this period the statutes providing for the establishment of segregated schools in cities of the first class “were no longer operative as laws”). But see *Bd. of Educ. of City of Ottawa v. Tinnon*, 26 Kan. 1, 18–19 (1881)(noting in dictum that the power to segregate schools has always existed in the city of Leavenworth, “from its earliest territorial days down to the present time”).

²¹ See Ch. 81, 1879 Kan. Sess. Laws 163 (repealed 1957). Cities of the first class could include prohibitions against segregation through special legislation. For example, the 1889 act providing for the incorporation of Wichita as a city of the first class banned segregation within the city’s public schools. See Ch. 227, 1889 Kan. Sess. Laws 329 (prohibiting discrimination on account of race or color in Wichita schools); *Rowles v. Bd. of Educ. of City of Wichita*, 91 P. 88 (Kan. 1907)(holding that the special act made it unlawful for separate schools to be established in Wichita). The law was amended in 1905 to allow for the establishment of segregated high schools in Kansas City, Kansas. See Ch. 414, 1905 Kan. Sess. Laws 676 (allowing for the establishment of segregated high schools in Kansas City, Kansas (repealed 1957)); *Richardson v. Bd. of Educ. of Kansas City*, 84 P. 538, 538 (Kan. 1906)(holding that the establishment of segregated high schools in Kansas City, Kansas was permissible under the 1905 law). This was apparently the result of exceptionally high racial tensions in Kansas City, Kansas. See Dave Peavler, *Drawing the Color Line in Kansas City: The Creation of Sumner High School*, Vol. 28, No. 3 Kansas History Autumn 2005, at 188.

²² See Ch. 389, 1957 Kan. Sess. Laws 847(repealing the law allowing for segregation in cities of the first class).

²³ See e.g. *Bd. of Educ. of City of Ottawa v. Tinnon*, 26 Kan. 1 (1881)(holding that the operation of separate schools in cities of the second class was not permissible under Kansas law). The *Tinnon* litigation has become famous in recent decades as “the earliest discoverable judicial statement that the Fourteenth Amendment prohibited legal segregation of public schools”. Andrew Kull, *A Nineteenth--Century Precursor of Brown v. Board of Education: The Trial Court Opinion in the Kansas School Segregation Case of 1881*, 68 Chi.-Kent L. Rev. 1199, 1201 (1993).

²⁴ *Whitlow v. Bd. of Educ. of City of Council Grove*, 196 P. 772 (Kan. 1921)(discussing, but not litigating, the establishment of a “colored” school in Council Grove); *Farmers' State Bank of Bonner Springs v. Sch. Dist. No. 100, Johnson County*, 4 P.2d 404, 405 (Kan. 1931)(discussing, but not litigating, the operation of a “colored” school in a rural school district in Johnson County). Separate schools were operated in cities where segregation had long been prohibited even in the period after the Supreme Court’s 1954 and 1955 *Brown* decisions. See *Cameron v. Bd. of Ed.*

allowed to continue, even when directly challenged through litigation.²⁵ At other times, the prohibition against impermissible segregation was enforced when challenged.²⁶

In 1954, *Brown v. Board* ended legal segregation in public schools.²⁷ However, communities across the country were able to maintain racially segregated schools through a variety of methods. The same was true in Kansas metropolitan areas, where city school districts expanded

of City of Bonner Springs, 318 P.2d 988, 989 (Kan. 1957). It was not unusual for impermissible school segregation to exist for years before finally challenged. *See e.g. Webb v. Sch. Dist. No. 90, Johnson County*, 206 P.2d 1066, 1068 (Kan. 1949)(noting that “years ago” the district in question had “unlawfully organized and established a separate grade school for the attendance of Negro children”).

²⁵ *See e.g. Jones v. McProud*, 64 P. 602, 602 (Kan. 1901)(denying admission to the local high school to colored students who had completed grade 8, on the basis that the lowest grade level in the high school was grade 10, and the school district had recently added grade 9 to the school for Black children, which was found not to be “inferior in standing” to the other schools in the district). Oskaloosa did not have a sufficient population to incorporate as a city of the first class. *See* U.S. Census 1900 (showing Oskaloosa to have a population of 978). *See also* PAUL FINKELMAN & STEPHEN E. GOTTLIEB, *TOWARD A USABLE PAST: LIBERTY UNDER STATE CONSTITUTIONS*, 233-39 (1991)(discussing pre-*Brown* desegregation cases in Kansas, including multiple district court decisions where unlawful segregation was allowed to continue despite being challenged in the courts).

²⁶ *Knox v. Bd. of Educ. of City of Indep.*, 25 P. 616, 617–19 (Kan. 1891)(holding that the legislature had not conferred the power to segregate schools on the basis of race to cities of the second class); *Williams v. Bd. of Educ. of City of Parsons*, 99 P. 216 (Kan. 1908)(holding that when a city establishes separate schools for “Colored” and White children “where the location of a school for one of these classes is such that access to it is beset with such dangers to life and limb that children of the class for which it is designated ought not to be required to attend it, such children are denied equal educational facilities); *Graham v. Bd. of Educ. of City of Topeka*, 114 P.2d 313 (Kan. 1941)(holding that separate grade structures in the racially segregated schools of Topeka constituted a denial of “equal treatment” guaranteed by the Kansas and United States constitutions).

²⁷ *Brown v. Bd. of Ed. of Topeka, Shawnee County, Kan.*, 347 U.S. 483, 495 (1954), *supplemented sub nom. Brown v. Bd. of Educ. of Topeka, Kan.*, 349 U.S. 294 (1955)(holding “that in the field of public education the doctrine of ‘separate but equal’ has no place” and that “separate educational facilities are inherently unequal”).

along with the suburbanizing White²⁸ population.²⁹ This allowed city school districts to maintain segregation through such practices as siting schools in racially homogenous areas and creating “optional attendance zones” in neighborhoods undergoing demographic transition.³⁰

In the mid-1960’s, desegregation began to be pursued more aggressively as Federal enforcement of *Brown v. Board* and successor cases increased. However, in many of the nation’s metropolitan areas, suburbanization and school district fragmentation allowed for segregation to be maintained along inter-district boundaries.³¹ During this decade, Kansas saw revolutionary changes to state-level school policies, creating what can best be described as Tiebout-like³²

²⁸ Residential segregation was maintained during eras of suburbanization through a variety of methods. In earlier periods, racially restrictive covenants acted to enforce residential segregation. *See e.g. Clark v. Vaughan*, 292 P. 783 (Kan. 1930)(discussing validity of racially restrictive covenants and determining that such provisions were generally valid, except where circumstances change to such a degree that enforcement is no longer equitable); Bruce D. Baker & Preston C. Green, *Kansas—Separate and Unequal by Design: What’s the Matter with the Rising State Role in Kansas Education?* In *THE RISING STATE: HOW STATE POWER IS TRANSFORMING OUR NATION’S SCHOOLS* 133. 137 (Bonnie C. Fusarelli & Bruce S. Cooper eds., 2009) (explaining that suburban housing in Kansas remained racially restrictive until at least 1962, despite the Supreme Court’s ruling in *Shelley v. Kraemer*, 334 U.S. 1 (1948)). From 1924 to at least the 1950’s real estate agents followed a “code of ethics” requiring the “steering” of households on the basis of race to certain neighborhoods. *See e.g. ROSE HELPER, RACIAL POLICIES AND PRACTICES OF REAL ESTATE BROKERS*, 201 (1969); DAVIS MCENTIRE, *RESIDENCE AND RACE*, 246 (1960)(noting that some local real estate boards interpreted a 1950 revision to the code which did not explicitly mention race to have the same meaning as the prior code). Additionally, racially discriminatory lending practices acted to maintain residential segregation. *See e.g. ROBERT LOUIS ROTENBERG & GARY W. McDONOGH*, 152 (1993)(detailing racially discriminatory lending practices during the 1970’s in Kansas City, Kansas).

²⁹ *See e.g. Brown v. Board of Educ. Of Topeka, Shawnee County, Kan.*, 892 F.2d 851 (1989)(mentioning effect of annexation of suburban areas by Topeka, and its effect on intra-district segregation after *Brown*. The annexations mentioned here occurred in the late 1950’s); RAYMOND WOLTERS, *RACE AND EDUCATION: 1954-2007*, 61-62 (2008) (noting intra-district “white flight”, or suburbanization, and intra-district segregation within the Topeka Public School District).

³⁰ *See e.g. Brown v. Board of Educ. Of Topeka*, 892 F.2d 851 (1989)(discussing that school closures, portable classrooms, and optional attendance zones were used to as methods to concentrate students of one race in certain schools and thereby acted to maintain segregation in Topeka during the 1950’s and 60’s); *United States v. Unified School District No. 500, Kansas City, Kansas*, 610 F.2d 688 (1979), at n. 7 (noting that over 50% of the Black students in the Kansas City, Kansas school district were assigned to schools that were greater than 98% Black. Two schools, Sumner High and Grant Elementary, were found to be 100% Black).

³¹ *See e.g. Erwin Chemerinsky, Ending The Dual System of American Public Education: The Urgent Need for Legislative Action*, 32 DePaul L.R. 77 (1982)(discussing segregation and inequality within public school systems in the nation’s major metropolitan areas).

³² *See Charles M. Tiebout, A Pure Theory of Local Expenditures*, 64 J. Pol. Econ. 416 (1956)(explaining the theoretical underpinnings of the Tiebout system); *See GREGORY K. INGRAM, EDUCATION, LAND, AND LOCATION*, 2-4 (2014)(linking the “Tiebout model” to fragmented school districts).

systems in Kansas metropolitan areas.³³ In such Tiebout metropolitan areas, the provision of public goods is fragmented between multiple jurisdictions.³⁴ Theoretically, in the Tiebout system households are able to choose a jurisdiction that provides the bundle of public goods the household prefers. In practice, the Tiebout system tends to result in housing prices becoming directly correlated to school quality or desirability.³⁵ Thus, “school choice” in a Tiebout system is exercised through the housing market.³⁶ Such systems allow for school segregation on the basis of race and socioeconomic status to continue on an inter-district level.³⁷

From the 1960’s onwards, Kansas metropolitan areas have experienced consistent suburbanization.³⁸ While central city school districts have seen continuous declines in enrollment, suburban school districts have seen continuous increases.³⁹ The quality of public schools in

³³ The first major wave of public-school reform in the aftermath of Brown included the 1963 School Unification Act. See Ch. 393, 1963 Kan. Sess. Law 901 (codified as Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-6734 (repealed 2003)); Baker, *supra* n. 29 at 135. The act promoted consolidation between rural, suburbanizing districts. However, consolidation between urban and suburbanizing districts was not encouraged. See Preston C. Green III et. al., *How the Kansas Courts Have Permitted and May Remedy Racial Funding Disparities in the Aftermath of Brown*, 53 Washburn L.J. 439, 441 (2014). Other laws enacted during this period which contributed to the creation of a Tiebout system include an amendment to the law governing city annexations. Previously the law had provided that cities and city school districts must have identical boundaries. See e.g. *Smith v. Board of Education of City of Pittsburg*, 278 P. 741 (1929)(holding that annexation by a city of a the first class of land, even land in the boundaries of a school district of a city of the second class, transfers school district jurisdiction to the school district of the city of the first class). However, the law was amended in 1965 so that annexation by a city did not extend city school district boundaries. See Ch. 420, 1965 Kan. Sess. Laws 977 (codified as Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-515)). Thus, mid-1960’s school reforms lead to the solidification of the boundaries separating urban and rural, suburbanizing districts.

³⁴ See e.g. Richard Briffault, *Our Localism: Part II-Localism and Legal Theory*, 90 Colum. L. Rev. 346, 402 (1990)(noting that “an endorsement of fragmentation” follows “directly from the Tiebout model); Douglas W. Kmiec & Eric L. Diamond, *New Federalism Is Not Enough: The Privatization of Non-Public Goods*, 7 Harv. J.L. & Pub. Policy 321, 351–61 (1984)(discussing the merits of jurisdictional fragmentation and the “Tiebout hypothesis”); Ingram *supra* n. 33.

³⁵ INGRAM *supra* n. 33 at 1 (noting that housing prices tend to reflect school quality).

³⁶ Erica Frankenberg, *Splintering School Districts: Understanding the Link Between Segregation and Fragmentation*, 34 L. & Soc. Inquiry 869, 871 (2009)(noting that “a form of school choice exists in moving to a different school district-for those who can afford to buy homes in districts considered to provide high-quality schools and do not face racial barriers in the housing market”).

³⁷ See e.g. Erika K. Wilson, *Toward A Theory of Equitable Federated Regionalism in Public Education*, 61 UCLA L. Rev. 1416, 1418 (2014)(discussing inter-district segregation in fragmented metropolitan areas and noting that fragmented school districts foster “exclusion based on race and class”).

³⁸ See e.g. Laurie Reynolds, *Intergovernmental Cooperation, Metropolitan Equity, and the New Regionalism*, 78 Wash. L. Rev. 93 (2003)(discussing increased suburbanization up through the 1990’s).

³⁹ For example, 29,115 students were enrolled in Kansas City Kansas Public Schools (KCKPS) in 1975. See . In 1980 23,425 students were enrolled in KCKPS. See THE INSTITUTE FOR SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES AT THE

suburban areas has likewise increased, while the relative desirability of central city schools has decreased.⁴⁰ The higher relative desirability of suburban schools is evidenced by the rising relative value of homes in suburban school districts compared to homes in urban school districts.⁴¹ The movement of educational resources to suburban school districts has been aided by state-level school funding formulas which have favored suburban school districts over central city school districts.⁴²

UNIVERSITY OF 1975 KANSAS, KANSAS STATISTICAL ABSTRACT, 104 (1975). In 1998 only 19,876 students were enrolled in KCKPS. *See* AUGENBLICK & MYERS, INC., A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE ORGANIZATION OF KANSAS SCHOOL DISTRICTS, Appendix I (2001), <https://zenodo.org/api/files/6d418a9d-16a3-477e-8a24-90b9009337fe/A%20comprehnsvive%20study%20KS%20school%20districts%202001.pdf>. Wichita Public Schools had an enrollment of around 68,000 in 1960. *See* Steven G. Rivkin, *Residential Segregation and School Integration*, 67 *Sociology of Education* 279, 287 (Oct. 1994). By 1980 enrollment fell to 42,350. *See* The University of Kansas INSTITUTE FOR POLICY AND SOCIAL RESEARCH, 1980 KANSAS STATISTICAL ABSTRACT, 79 (Wendy A. Murray ed., 1980). During the 1970's enrollment in Topeka Public Schools fell by more than 30%. *See* RAYMOND WOLTERS, THE BURDEN OF BROWN: THIRTY YEARS OF SCHOOL DESEGREGATION, 262 (1992). Meanwhile suburban school districts saw rapid growth. For example, USD 437 grew from 2,460 students in 1980 to nearly 5,000 students by 1998. *See* AUGENBLICK & MYERS, INC., at Appendix I. USD 266, a suburban district in the Wichita metropolitan area had an enrollment of only 967 in 1980. *See* 1980 Kansas Statistical Abstract at 79. By 1989 enrollment had more than doubled to 2,1970 students and would more than double again to 4,895 students in 1998. *See* AUGENBLICK & MYERS, INC., DISTRICTS at Appendix I.

⁴⁰ *See id.*

⁴¹ *See e.g.* *See e.g.* U.S. Census of Housing (1960)(noting that the suburban to city home value ration in the Topeka metropolitan areas was 95%); U.S. Census of Housing (1970)(noting that the suburban to city home value ratio in Topeka was 140%).

⁴² After the 1963 School Unification Act, school funding underwent major reforms under the 1965 School Foundation Act. *See* Charles Berger, *Equity Without Adjudication: Kansas School Finance Reform and the 1992 School District Finance and Quality Performance Act*, 27 *J.L. & Educ.* 1, 6 (1998). A pupil to teacher multiplier in the act disadvantaged larger, city school districts by directing significantly more state funding to smaller, rural and suburbanizing districts. *See* Baker *supra* n. 29 at 138-39. Additionally, the act disadvantaged poor school districts in rich counties. *See Id.*; Ch. 402, Kan. Sess. Laws 1965 (codified at Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-7001 to -7024 (repealed 1973)). This may have harmed urban school districts as housing wealth became increasingly suburbanized. *See Supra* n. 42. Subsequent school financing schemes have also tended to hurt poorer school districts. For example, The School District Equalization Act (SDEA) contained a provision restricting the authority of school districts to raise their budgets from year to year, prohibiting school districts with lower budgets from catching up to school districts with higher budgets. *See* Charles Berger, *Equity Without Adjudication: Kansas School Finance Reform and the 1992 School District Finance and Quality Performance Act*, 27 *J.L. & Educ.* 1, 12 (1998). *See also* Ch. 292, 1973 Kan. Sess. Laws 969 (codified at Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-7030 to -7036 (repealed 1992)). Additionally, the SDEA provided higher levels of base funding to districts with smaller enrollments than to districts with large student populations. *See* Baker *supra* n. 29 at 139-40. The 1992 School District Finance and Quality Performance Accreditation Act (SDFQPA) “froze into place prior disparities”, by, for example, setting a strict revenue cap on school districts and providing a 25% adjustment for the number of children attending new school facilities, which was initially only received by children in suburban school districts. *See* Rising State p. 141 (discussing the SDFQPA). *See also* Ch. 280, 1992 Kan. Sess. Laws 1691 (codified as Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-6405 to -6440 (repealed 2015)). In 2015, SDFQPA was replaced with the Classroom Learning Assuring Student Success Act (CLASS) funding system. *See* Ch. 4, 2015 Kan. Sess. Laws 34 (codified at Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-6463 to -6481 & 72-6483 to -6485 (held unconstitutional by *Gannon v.*

Inequitable funding formulas have been challenged and found unconstitutional in multiple rounds of litigation since the 1970's.⁴³ The legislature has, both voluntarily and in response to legal challenges, raised nominal funding per pupil on a statewide level. For school districts in central cities, specific funding for low-income or high cost pupils has been provided through mechanisms such as the “at-risk pupil” weighting found in recent school funding formulas.⁴⁴ Despite these measures, a significant achievement gap remains between central city and suburban school districts in the state’s metropolitan areas.⁴⁵ Furthermore, housing values in Kansas suburban districts continue to be much higher than housing values in central city districts.⁴⁶ As a result, lower-income

State, 390 P.3d 461 (Kan. 2017)). CLASS was found to exacerbate wealth-based disparities between school districts. *Gannon v. State*, 390 P.3d 461 (Kan. 2017). CLASS was replaced by the Kansas School Equity and Enhancement Act (KSEEA) in 2017. *See* Ch. 95, 2017 Kan. Sess. Laws 983-84 (codified at Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-5131 to -5176 (held unconstitutional by *Gannon v. State*, 402 P.3d 513 (Kan. 2017))). The funding formula in KSEEA was almost identical to the funding formula in the SDFQPA immediately prior to its repeal. *Gannon v. State*, 402 P.3d 513, 522 (Kan. 2017). The formula in the KSEEA and related statutes increased spending flexibility, but also increased wealth-based disparities. *See Gannon v. State*, 402 P.3d 513, 544 (Kan. 2017).

⁴³ The first challenge to school funding laws occurred in 1972, with a district court holding that the School Foundation Act was unconstitutional under the Kansas Constitution. *See* Richard E. Levy, *Gunfight at the K-12 Corral: Legislative vs. Judicial Power in the Kansas School Finance Litigation*, 54 U. Kan. L. Rev. 1021, 1035–37 (2006)(discussing the *Caldwell*, *Knowles*, and *Mock* decisions); *Caldwell v. State*, No. 50616, slip op. (Kan. Dist. Ct. Johnson County, Aug. 30, 1972); *Knowles v. State Bd. of Educ.*, No. 77CV251, slip op. (Kan. Dist. Ct. Shawnee County, Jan. 26, 1981); *Mock v. State*, No. 91-CV-1009, slip op. (Kan. Dist. Ct. Shawnee County, Oct. 14, 1991). *See also Montoy v. State*, 138 P.3d 755 (Kan. 2006)(providing summary of Montoy series of litigation and holding funding formula was constitutional); *Gannon v. State*, 402 P.3d 513 (Kan. 2017)(providing background to Gannon litigation and holding that the state’s funding formula failed to constitutionally fund schools).

⁴⁴ *See e.g.* Levy, *supra* n.44 at 1038 (discussing enrollment weighting, including at-risk weighting, under the SDFQPA).

⁴⁵ For example, graduation rates are consistently higher in suburban districts compared to central city school districts. For the 2016-17 school year the graduation rate in Topeka Public Schools was 77.4% while the graduation rate in the Auburn-Washburn school district was 94.4%. The graduation rate in Wichita Public Schools was 73.9% while the graduation rate in the Maize school district was 91.9%. The graduation rate for the Kansas City Kansas Public Schools district was 71.0% while the graduation rate in the Piper school district was 92.7%. *See* KSDE Data Central, *2016-2017 State Graduation Rate – Four Year Adjusted Cohort Formula by District Race, and Gender (All Schools)*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, available at https://zenodo.org/record/1170511/files/KSDE%20Data%20on%20Grad%20Rate%202016_17.pdf.

⁴⁶ For example, in 2016, the median home value in the Topeka Public Schools district was \$87,100. In the Auburn-Washburn district the median home value was \$177,600. In the Wichita Public Schools district median housing value was \$103,000. In the Maize school district median housing value was \$179,200. In the Kansas City Kansas Public Schools district, the median home value was \$78,500. In the Piper school district median home value was \$207,300. *See* 2012-2016 American Community Survey, *5-Year Estimates: Owner Occupied Housing (Median Value in Dollars) Kansas School Districts*, U.S. CENSUS BUREAU available at <https://zenodo.org/record/1170511/files/housing%20value%20KS%20school%20districts%202016.pdf>.

families may be unable to move to suburban school districts with high performing schools.⁴⁷ Thus, households in poverty and low-income households tend to be concentrated in central city districts.⁴⁸ Due to the correlation between income and racial or ethnic group, central city districts tend to enroll relatively more minority students compared to suburban districts.⁴⁹ In 2014, the Kansas Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarships Program was enacted to help families who are unable to exercise school choice through the housing market or enrollment in private schools.⁵⁰ Theoretically, the program could contribute to equality of educational opportunity by disentangling housing and school attendance.⁵¹

II. Tax Credit Scholarship Programs and the Kansas Program

The first part of this section provides an overview of the tax credit scholarship programs. The second part of this section provides a general introduction to the Kansas Tax Credit Scholarship for Low Income Students Program.

⁴⁷ Lower income families may be unable to move to high performing suburban districts due to housing costs. *See Id. See also Ingram supra* n. 33.

⁴⁸ For example, for the 2017-18 school year 69% of students in the Topeka Public Schools district were approved for free lunches while 24% of students were approved in the Auburn-Washburn school district. In the Wichita Public Schools district 63.5% of students were approved, while in the Maize school district 13.3% of students qualified. In the Kansas City Kansas Public Schools district 76.1% of students were approved while in the Piper school district 15.7% of the student population qualified. *See* KSDE Data Central, *2016-2017-2018 State Students Approved for Free – or Reduced-Price Lunches by District (All Schools)*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, available at https://zenodo.org/record/1170511/files/KSDE%20Data_STudents%20Approved%20for%20Free%20or%20Reduced%20Lunch%2C%202017_18.pdf.

⁴⁹ For example, in 2016 minorities accounted for 24.5% of the total population within the Topeka Public Schools district and 12% of the total population within the Auburn-Washburn school district. Minorities accounted for around 26% of the total population within the Wichita Public Schools district and around 9% of the total population in the Maize school district. Minorities accounted for about 45% of the total population in the Kansas City Kansas school district and 21% of the total population in the Piper school district. *See* 2012-2016 American Community Survey, *5-Year Estimates: Race (Total Population) Kansas School Districts*, U.S. CENSUS BUREAU, available at <https://zenodo.org/record/1170511/files/racial%20compisition%20of%20Kansas%20school%20district%202016.pdf>.

⁵⁰ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4353 (West)(stating that the act is to provide opportunity to eligible students and their parents).

⁵¹ *See* James E. Ryan & Michael Heise, *The Political Economy of School Choice*, 111 Yale L.J. 2043, 2045–46 (2002)(noting school choice programs may threaten suburban home values as housing becomes delinked from access to quality schools).

a. Introduction to Tax Credit Scholarship Programs

Tax credit scholarship programs are a form of private school choice.⁵² The programs work by issuing tax credits to taxpayers who make donations to state approved non-profit “scholarship-granting” organizations (SGOs).⁵³ These organizations in turn provide scholarships for students to attend private schools. Thus, the programs use public funds to subsidize education in private schools through the use of “tax expenditures”.⁵⁴

Arizona adopted the first tax credit scholarship program in 1997.⁵⁵ In the 20 years since, 17 additional states have implemented similar programs⁵⁶, most recently Illinois in 2017.⁵⁷

⁵² It appears that all programs allow for participating students to apply scholarships to private schools. Some states allow students to apply scholarships toward public schools, if an SGO works with a public school and the public school is willing to accept the student. *See e.g.* Pa. Stat. Ann. tit. 24, § 20-2002-B (West).

⁵³ KEVIN G. WELNER, *NEOVOUCHERS: THE EMERGENCE OF TUITION TAX CREDITS FOR SCHOOLING* (2008), 6. These organizations are given a variety of names under different programs. *See e.g.* La. Stat. Ann. § 47:6301(B)(1)(a)(labeling SGOs “school tuition organization”); N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 77-G:5 (labeling SGOs “scholarship organization”); Pa. Stat. Ann. tit. 24, § 20-2002-B (West) (labeling some SGOs “opportunity scholarship organization”).

⁵⁴ *See generally* CHRISTOPHER HOWARD, *THE HIDDEN WELFARE STATE: TAX EXPENDITURES AND SOCIAL POLICY IN THE UNITED STATES* (1999) (discussing use of tax expenditures as subsidies for favored activities or practices). *See also* James G. Dwyer, *No Accounting for School Vouchers*, 48 Wake Forest L. Rev. 361 (2013)(noting that a tax credit scholarship program “essentially allows taxpayers to designate use of some of the taxes they owe”); Welner *supra* n. 53 AT 29-32 (discussing tax expenditures in relation to tax credit scholarship programs).

⁵⁵ Stephen D. Sugarman, *Tax Credit School Scholarship Plans*, 43 J.L. & Educ. 1, 1-2 (2014). *See also* Ariz. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 43-1089 (noting that the statute was originally added as § 43-1087 by Laws 1997, Ch. 48, § 2).

⁵⁶ Ala. Code § 16-6D-1 (Alabama Accountability Act of 2013); Fla. Stat. Ann. § 1002.395 (Florida Tax Credit Scholarship Program); Ga. Code Ann. § 48-7-29.16 (Georgia Credit for Qualified Education Expenses); 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/1 (Illinois Invest in Kids Act); Iowa Code Ann. § 422.11S (Iowa School Tuition Organization Tax Credit); Ind. Code Ann. § 6-3.1-30.5 (Indiana School Scholarship Tax Credit); Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4351 (Kansas Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarship Program Act); La. Stat. Ann. § 47:6301 (Louisiana Credits for Donations to School Tuition Organizations); Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3101 (Montana Tax Credit for Qualified Education Contributions); N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 77-G:1 (New Hampshire Education Tax Credit); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.250 (Nevada Educational Choice Scholarship Program); Okla. Stat. Ann. tit. 68, § 2357.206 (Oklahoma Equal Opportunity Education Scholarship Act); Pa. Stat. Ann. tit. 24, § 20-2001-B (Pennsylvania Educational Improvement and Opportunity Scholarship Tax Credits); 44 R.I. Gen. Laws Ann. § 44-62-1 (Rhode Island Tax Credit for Contributions to a Scholarship Organization); 2017 SC H.B. 3720 Proviso 109.11 *available at* <http://www.eoc.sc.gov/Home/ECENC%202017/ECENC%20info%20posted%2006132017/Proviso%20109.pdf>. (South Carolina Educational Credit for Exceptional Needs Children); S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-2 (South Dakota Partners in Education Tax Credit Program); Va. Code Ann. § 58.1-439.25 (Virginia Education Improvement Scholarship Tax Credits).

⁵⁷ The Illinois program was enacted in 2017. The first school year for which scholarships will be available is the 2018-19 school year. Applications for scholarships opened on January 31, 2018. *See* Drew Zimmerman, *Applications Open for Private School Scholarship Program*, DEKALB COUNTY DAILY CHRONICLE, Jan. 30, 2018, <http://www.daily-chronicle.com/2018/01/30/applications-open-for-private-school-scholarship-program/a9ip73j/>.

Additionally, multiple states are currently considering⁵⁸, or have recently considered⁵⁹, adopting tax credit scholarship programs, and there has been a recent push for a federal program.⁶⁰ There is great variation among the different programs⁶¹ concerning value of the tax credit⁶², the class of taxpayers that can claim the credit⁶³, how the state tax credit interacts with federal tax credits or

⁵⁸ States considering a tax credit scholarship program during the 2018 legislative session include Kentucky *see e.g.* Tim Benson, *Research & Commentary: Tax-Credit Scholarships Would be a Good First Step for School Choice in Kentucky*, HEARTLAND INSTITUTE, Jan. 24, 2018, <https://www.heartland.org/publications-resources/publications/research--commentary-tax-credit-scholarships-would-be-a-good-first-step-for-school-choice-in-kentucky> (discussing a Kentucky program that is under consideration); Martha Stoddard, *If Nebraska Legislature Debates School Choice Bill, the Price Tag Could be a Snag*, OMAHA WORLD-HAROLD, Jan. 16, 2018, http://www.omaha.com/news/legislature/if-nebraska-legislature-debates-school-choice-bill-the-price-tag/article_2a462c28-79eb-5cce-a44f-95d21fee4890.html (discussing a potential Nebraska program currently under consideration).

⁵⁹ States considering a program during their 2017 legislative included: Texas. *See* 2017 Texas Senate Bill No. 2, Texas Eighty-Fifth Legislature - 1st Session Called. Wyoming. *See* 2017 Wyoming House Bill No. 150, Wyoming Sixty-Fourth Legislature - 2017 General Session. . 2017. Missouri. *See* Missouri Senate Bill No. 32, Missouri Ninety-Ninth General Assembly, First Regular Session. Idaho. *See* 2017 Idaho House Bill No. 234, Idaho Sixty-Fourth Idaho Legislature, First Regular Session – 2017. Mississippi. *See* 2017 Mississippi House Bill No. 1703, Mississippi One Hundred Thirty-Second Legislative Session. Hawaii. *See* Hawaii Senate Bill No. 2606, Hawaii Twenty-Ninth Legislature - Regular Session of 2018.

⁶⁰ *See e.g.* Sally Ho, *DeVos Says School Vouchers Could be Part of Federal Tax Overhaul Discussions*, ASSOCIATED PRESS, Aug. 11, 2017, <https://www.apnews.com/9b19f16f1a5240f190f2c79f5f41a97c>.

⁶¹ *See generally* Hillel Y. Levin, *Tax Credit Scholarship Programs and the Changing Ecology of Public Education*, 45 *Ariz. St. L.J.* 1033, 1052-61 (2013)(discussing some of the differences between the Alabama, Florida, Louisiana, Indiana, Iowa, Virginia, Pennsylvania, Rhode Island, Oklahoma, New Hampshire, Arizona, and Georgia programs); Sugarman *supra* n. 55 (discussing the various provisions that tax credit scholarship programs can contain, and the possible effects that such provisions can have); Welner *supra* n. 53 at 39—56 (discussing the Arizona, Pennsylvania, and Florida programs).

⁶² Multiple states value the tax credit at 100% of the taxpayer donation. *See e.g.* Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3111 (setting value of tax credit equal to value of donation). Oklahoma and Indiana currently have the lowest valued tax credit at 50% for a one-year donation. *See* Okla. Stat. Ann. tit. 68, § 2357.206(B)(1) (West); Ind. Code Ann. § 6-3.1-30.5-8 (West). In some programs tax credits are given more value if taxpayers pledge to make donations for a two-year period. *See e.g.* Pa. Stat. Ann. tit. 24, § 20-2005-B (valuing credits at 75% of the value of donation for one-year donations and 90% of the value of donation for two-year donation commitments).

⁶³ Some states may allow only certain businesses to claim credits. *See e.g.* N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 77-G:1 (allowing the credit to be claimed by a “business organization or business enterprise”). Some states may allow only individual taxpayers to claim the credit. *See e.g.* Sugarman *supra* n. 55 at 9 (2014)(noting that the Arizona program initially only allowed for individuals to claim credits). Other states allow both individuals and businesses to claim the credit. *See e.g.* Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3111 (allowing a corporation or “taxpayer” to claim the credit, with taxpayer being defined as including “any person”). Some states raise scholarship funds by issuing different tax credits to different types of taxpayers through separate programs. *See e.g.* Ariz. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 43-1089 (individuals); Ariz. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 43-1183 (corporations).

deductions⁶⁴, the maximum or minimum value of tax credits an individual taxpayer can claim,⁶⁵ the maximum total value of tax credits available under the program⁶⁶, students eligible to receive

⁶⁴ Some states may allow taxpayers to claim the state tax credit and a federal tax deduction for the same donation, while others prohibit this practice. *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/10(d)(providing that “no credit shall be taken under this Act for any qualified contribution for which a taxpayer claims a federal income tax deduction); La. Stat. Ann. § 47:6301(A)(1)(a) (providing that “the credit may be used in addition to any federal tax credit or deduction). *See also* Erica L. Green, *In Some States, Donating to Private Schools Can Earn You a Profit*, N.Y. TIMES, May, 17 2017, <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/05/17/us/politics/in-some-states-donating-to-private-schools-can-earn-you-a-profit.html> (noting how in some states, this allows donors to “earn a profit” on their donations).

⁶⁵ *See e.g.* Okla. Stat. Ann. tit. 68, § 2357.206(B) (establishing a maximum credit of \$1,000 for single individuals, \$2,000 for married individuals filing jointly, and \$100,000 for any taxpayer that is a legal business entity); Va. Code Ann. § 58.1-439.26 (establishing a maximum credit value of \$125,000 and a minimum credit of \$500); Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3111(setting maximum credit value at \$150); N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 77-G:3 (setting maximum tax credit value at 10 percent of the value of the permitted total value of program tax credits).

⁶⁶ *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/10(b)(capping the total value of program tax credits at \$75,000,000 or \$100,000,000 dollars in donations with credits valued at 75% of donation value). Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3111(5)(a)(i) (setting the initial total value of program tax credits at \$3,000,000 with credits valued at 100% donation value); Fla. Stat. Ann. § 1002.395 (West) (capping the total value of program credits at \$229,000,000 with credits valued at 100% of donation value).

scholarships⁶⁷, the value of scholarships⁶⁸, and regulations placed on SGOs⁶⁹ and private schools⁷⁰ that participate in the program.

⁶⁷ For example, many programs are means-tested, limiting the household income of eligible students to some maximum level. *See e.g.* 44 R.I. Gen. Laws Ann. § 44-62-2 (providing that eligible students must be a member of a household with an annual household income of not more than 250% of the federal poverty guidelines). Eligibility for other programs is not means-tested. *See e.g.* Ga. Code Ann. § 20-2A-1(1) (West)(defining “eligible student” without reference to household income). Another approach programs take is to require a certain number of scholarships be awarded to students whose eligibility is means tested. *See e.g.* N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 77-G:2(I)(d) (requiring at least 40% of scholarships to be awarded to students who qualified for the federal free and reduced-price meal program in the final year they were in public school). Programs may also limit scholarship values based on a student’s household income. *See e.g.* Fla. Stat. Ann. § 1002.395(b). A few programs tie continued eligibility to income. *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5 (requiring household income not exceed 400% poverty levels for continued student eligibility). Additionally, some programs may require students to have previously been enrolled in public schools. *See e.g.* Va. Code Ann. § 58.1-439.25 (West)(requiring certain students seeking a scholarship to have been enrolled in public school for at least half of the prior school year). While other programs may not be targeted specifically to students currently attending public schools. *See e.g.* Iowa Code Ann. § 422.11S (West)(defining eligible student without reference to public school enrollment). Others may limit eligible students to those who attend or would attend a low-performing public school. *See e.g.* Pa. Stat. Ann. tit. 24, § 20-2002-B (West) (limiting recipients of the Pennsylvania “Opportunity Scholarship” to students who live in the attendance zone of low performing schools). Some programs may use a variety of factors when determining student eligibility, including income and prior public-school enrollment in a low performing school. *See e.g.* K.S.A. § 72-4352(d).

⁶⁸ Programs take multiple approaches in setting scholarship values. Some states tie maximum scholarship amount to the state expenditures per pupil. *See e.g.* Va. Code Ann. § 58.1-439.28 (West)(setting the maximum scholarship amount at 100% of certain state funds per-pupil provided to the public school the student would otherwise attend). Some states simply establish flat maximums. *See e.g.* Ala. Code § 16-6D-4 (West) (allowing for maximum grants of \$6,000 to elementary school students, \$8,000 for middle school students, and \$10,000 for high school students) Some states establish a flat maximum with provisions to increase the maximum in reference to inflation. *See e.g.* Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West)(setting the maximum scholarship value at \$7,755, but allowing for increased maximum value as determined in reference to the Consumer Price Index). Other program’s provisions on scholarship value set scholarship amounts at either a flat maximum or a percentage of state expenditures per pupil, depending on which is higher. *See e.g.* Okla. Stat. Ann. tit. 68, § 2357.206(G)(3)(b) (setting the maximum value of a scholarship at the greater of \$5,000 or 80% of “statewide annual average per-pupil expenditure”). Still others set both a maximum scholarship value and maximum average scholarship value. *See* Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3103 (setting maximum scholarship value at 50% per-pupil average of total public-school expenditures and maximum average scholarship value at 30% of the per-pupil average of total public-school expenditures). While some set only a maximum average scholarship value. N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 77-G:2(b)(setting the maximum average scholarship value at \$2,500, without specifying a maximum scholarship value). Only a few programs set any sort of scholarship minimums. *See e.g.* Fla. Stat. Ann. § 1002.395(12)(a) (providing that scholarship amount shall be for total costs, as long as they do not exceed annual limits under the program).

⁶⁹ For example, different programs may require SGOs to apply a different percentage of donations to the funding of scholarships. *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5 (requiring SGOs to use at least 95% of donations for scholarships); S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-4 (requiring SGOs to spend at least 90% of contributions on scholarship awards); Pa. Stat. Ann. tit. 24, § 20-2002-B (West) (requiring “opportunity scholarship organizations” to spend at least 80% of contributions on an “opportunity scholarship program”). The discretion of SGOs in allocating scholarships may also differ. *See e.g.* La. Stat. Ann. § 47:6301 (requiring SGOs to grant scholarships on a first come, first served basis); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270(f) (West) (must not limit scholarships to one school); Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3103(1)(b) (prohibiting SGOs from limiting scholarships to a “particular type” of school). Some programs require SGOs to undertake a certain level of community outreach. *See e.g.* La. Stat. Ann. § 47:6301(c)(xi) (requiring SGOs to “adequately advertise” the availability of scholarships to the public).

⁷⁰ For example, some states require participating private schools be accredited either by the state public education agency or a state approved accreditation association. *See e.g.* Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3102(b)

Tax credit scholarship programs are similar to voucher programs, even garnering the labels “voucher-like”⁷¹, “neovouchers”⁷², and “backdoor vouchers”⁷³. However, there are some key differences between vouchers and tax credit scholarships. Politically, tax credit scholarships are much more popular than vouchers among the public.⁷⁴ Furthermore, unlike vouchers, tax credit scholarships create “institutionalized constituencies” which act to defend tax credit scholarship programs once they are established.⁷⁵ Additionally, tax credit scholarships are perhaps more likely to be found constitutional under state constitutional provisions.⁷⁶ Perhaps due to these advantages,

(requiring participating private schools to either be accredited, be seeking accreditation, or inform participating students’ parents in writing that the school is not accredited or seeking accreditation). Some states require participating private schools to administer some type of assessment tests *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/50(2)(B) (requiring participating private schools to administer assessments “in the same manner in which they are administered in public schools”); Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3102(d) (requiring schools to administer a “nationally recognized standardized assessment test or criterion-referenced test). Programs’ may include provisions that explicitly prohibit certain types of discrimination. *See e.g.* Ariz. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 43-1601 (requiring that participating private schools do not discriminate on the basis of race, color, disability, familial status or national origin). Additionally, different programs may place certain requirements on teachers or other school employees at participating private schools. *See e.g.* Fla. Stat. Ann. § 1002.421 (West)(requiring private schools to employ or contract with teachers who have at least three years teaching experience or some special expertise and requiring private schools to subject each employee or contracted personnel with direct student contact to a national background screening).

⁷¹ *See e.g.* Julie F. Mead, *The Right to an Education or the Right to Shop for Schooling: Examining Voucher Programs in Relation to State Constitutional Guarantees*, 42 Fordham Urb. L.J. 703, 705 (2015).

⁷² *See Welner supra* n. 53.

⁷³ *See e.g.* Erie Zoru, *Column: Put the Brakes on GOP’s Backdoor Voucher Idea*, CHICAGO TRIBUNE, Jan. 24, 2017, <http://www.chicagotribune.com/news/opinion/zorn/ct-perspec-zorn-education-taxcredit-neovouchers-20170824-story.html>.

⁷⁴ *See e.g.* Matt Barnum, *How to Rile Up Education Debates with One Word*, THEATLANTIC.COM, Jan. 19, 2018, <https://www.theatlantic.com/education/archive/2018/01/how-to-rile-up-education-debates-with-one-word/550856/> (noting that support was much higher for “scholarship tax credits” than for school vouchers); Adele Robinson, *Risky Credit: Tuition Tax Credits and Issues of Accountability and Equity*, 11 Stan. L. & Policy Rev. 253, 260-63 (2000)(noting that tax credits “blunt” many of the difficult political questions surrounding school choice and that the structure of such programs may allow for greater government support for private schools than would be acceptable under traditional vouchers).

⁷⁵ Welner *supra* n. 53 at 93 (noting that the long-term survival of tax credit scholarships is enhanced by the institutionalization of a political constituency through the formation of the nonprofit corporations that carry out policy).

⁷⁶ For example, tax credit scholarships are more likely to be found constitutional when challenged under Blaine Amendments and similar clauses. *See e.g.* Jonathan D. Boyer, *Education Tax Credits: School Choice Initiatives Capable of Surmounting Blaine Amendments*, 43 Colum. J.L. & Soc. Probs. 117 (2009); William G. Frey & Virginia Lynn Hogben, *Vouchers, Tuition Tax Credits, and Scholarship-Donation Tax Credits: A Constitutional and Practical Analysis*, 31 Stetson L. Rev. 165, 190 (2002)(noting that tax credit scholarships avoid the constitutional problems inherent in appropriating tax dollars for use at religious institutions). *See also Kotterman v. Killian*, 972 P.2d 606 (Ariz. 1999)(holding that the tax credit is not an “appropriation of public money” to aid sectarian schools for purposes of the state constitution). Additionally, traditional voucher programs have been found unconstitutional under a strict “uniformity” clause. *See Bush v. Holmes*, 919 So. 2d 392, 412 (Fla. 2006)(holding that an Florida traditional voucher program was unconstitutional due to violation of the state constitutions education clause which place a “paramount

tax credit scholarship programs are currently much more widespread than traditional voucher programs.⁷⁷

Proponents argue that Tax credit scholarship programs have multiple positive effects on society.⁷⁸ One theorized benefit is that such programs can increase school choice for students, especially for students who would not have otherwise been able to exercise choice.⁷⁹ Proponents of such programs claim that increased school choice will lead to better student outcomes⁸⁰, as students are able to escape “failing” public schools⁸¹. Furthermore, the increase in ability to exercise school choice may improve public schools through increased competition.⁸² Additionally,

duty” on the state to make “adequate provision” for a “uniform, safe, secure, and high quality system of free public schools”). *But see Davis v. Grover*, 480 N.W.2d 460 (Wis. 1992)(holding that a Wisconsin voucher program complied with the state’s uniformity clause which required the legislature provide for the establishment of district schools as nearly uniform as possible).

⁷⁷ See e.g. Sugarman *supra* n. 55 at 1 (noting that many more students participate in tax credit scholarship programs than in traditional voucher programs).

⁷⁸ See e.g. *Expanding Tax Credit Scholarships for Low Income Students Program: Hearing on H.B. 2374 Before the Kansas House Education Committee*, 2017 Legis. Sess. (Kan. 2017) (testimony of David Dorsey, Senior Education Policy Analyst Kansas Policy Institute), http://www.kslegislature.org/li/b2017_18/committees/ctte_h_ed_1/documents/testimony/20170323_08.pdf.

⁷⁹ See e.g. *Id.*; (claiming that students – particularly students in low-income families – find themselves stuck in low performing schools and unable to escape them simply because of their address).

⁸⁰ See e.g. David Dorsey, *Low Income Students Are Doing Better in KS Private Schools – School Choice Week*, KANSAS POLICY INSTITUTE, Jan. 22, 2018 (claiming that since low-income students currently enrolled in private schools tend to perform better than low-income students in public school districts, that expanding the tax credit scholarship program would improve outcomes and provide opportunity for all students). Of course, this logic ignores the possibility that the difference in results could be due to factors such as private school admission standards or the general tendency for students from households that already emphasize education and are willing to invest additional resources in education. See Welner *supra* n. 53 (explaining that parents with “the most education, wealth, and involvement in their children’s education” are more likely to exercise active choice and that the effect of a tax credit scholarship policy is “to provide an alternative to a subpopulation skewed toward the best behaved and highest-scoring students”).

⁸¹ See *id.*

⁸² See e.g. Bart Goering, *How to Really Improve Education in Kansas*, WICHITA EAGLE, Sep. 27, 2016 (stating that competition would fix Kansas schools, since competition works in the private sector); Cassandra M.D. Hart and David Figlio, *Does Competition Improve Public Schools*, EDUCATION NEXT, Winter 2011, at 74 (attributing a slight increase in test scores for students in certain Florida public schools over the 2000 to 2007 time period to the competition created by the Florida tax credit scholarship program).

tax credit scholarship programs may save the states' money⁸³ if donations per scholarship receiving students is less than the state expends per pupil in public schools.⁸⁴

However, it is not entirely clear that tax credit scholarship programs deliver all of these benefits.⁸⁵ For example, depending on the number of “switchers”⁸⁶ programs may not lead to much of an increase in the exercise of choice and could be costing states more money than they would otherwise spend.⁸⁷ Additionally, the programs have suffered from lack of transparency, accountability, and oversight.⁸⁸ Furthermore, tax credit scholarship programs privatize education policymaking⁸⁹, which could have harmful effects. Finally, tax credit scholarship programs and other forms of school choice may hurt traditional public schools and the students who are unable to exercise choice.⁹⁰ However, each program is unique and should be analyzed on an individual basis.⁹¹

⁸³ *Expanding the Tax Credit Scholarships for Low Income Students Program: Hearing on H.B. 2457 Before the Kansas House Education Committee*, 2016 Legis. Sess. (Kan. 2016) (testimony of James Franko Vice President Kansas Policy Institute)(*claiming school choice programs and the Kansas program can save taxpayers money*).

⁸⁴ *See infra* n. 87.

⁸⁵ For example, some studies have found that students participating in voucher and voucher-like programs performed worse than eligible students who did not participate and continued to attend public schools. *See e.g.* CENTER FOR TAX AND BUDGET ACCOUNTABILITY, ANALYSIS OF INDIANA SCHOOL CHOICE PROGRAM (2015).

⁸⁶ True “switchers” are students that are moving from public school to private school or are entering kindergarten and would be attending public school if not for the subsidized private school tuition. *See Nevouchers* (ch. 4)

⁸⁷ If the number of switchers is less than half of the number of total participants, then the program will lose money compared to if the program had not been in operation. *See Welner supra* n. 53 at 86.

⁸⁸ *See e.g. See e.g.* Southern Education Foundation, *A Failed Experiment: Georgia's Tax Credit Scholarships for Private Schools*, <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED535565.pdf>; Arianna Prothero, *'There is no Oversight': Private School Vouchers Can Leave Parents on Their Own*, EDUCATION WEEK, Nov. 14, 2017, <https://www.edweek.org/ew/articles/2017/11/15/there-is-no-oversight-private-school-vouchers-can.html>; Institute on Taxation and Economic Policy, *Public Loss Private Gain: How School Voucher Tax Shelters Undermine Public Education*, ITEP.ORG, May 17, 2017, <https://itep.org/public-loss-private-gain-how-school-voucher-tax-shelters-undermine-public-education/>.

⁸⁹ *See e.g.* Dwyer *supra* n. 55 at 381 (2013) (noting that tax credit scholarship programs “make decision making” over the allocation of public funds “entirely private”).

⁹⁰ *See e.g.* Jennifer Smith Richards & Juan Perez Jr., *Chicago's Neighborhood Schools Hurting as Choice Abounds*, CHICAGO TRIBUNE, Jan. 8, 2016, <http://www.chicagotribune.com/news/ct-chicago-schools-choice-neighborhood-enrollment-met-20160108-story.html> (noting that choice is “hurting” traditional neighborhood schools).

⁹¹ Levin *supra* n. 62 at 1037 (explaining that tax credit scholarship programs “differ fundamentally from one another in form and function”).

b. Introduction to the Kansas Program

The Kansas program was established and is governed by the tax credit for low income students scholarship program originally enacted in 2014.⁹² The stated purpose of the act is to provide “eligible students” with an opportunity to attend schools of their parents’ choice.⁹³ The Kansas program values tax credits at 70% of donation value.⁹⁴ The program appears by implication to allow taxpayers to claim both the state tax credit and a federal tax deduction.⁹⁵ Both businesses and individuals may claim the tax credit.⁹⁶ The maximum value of credits an individual taxpayer can claim is \$500,000, while no minimum credit is specified.⁹⁷ The maximum aggregate value of credits issued through the program cannot exceed \$10,000,000, or around 14,300,000 in donations, for any one tax year.⁹⁸

To be eligible for a scholarship under the program, students must belong to a household with household income that does not exceed 100% of the maximum income permitted to qualify for the federal free lunch program.⁹⁹ Additionally, to be eligible students must live in the attendance zone of a low performing public school.¹⁰⁰ Student must also have been enrolled in any public school in the school year prior to the year in which a scholarship is first sought.¹⁰¹ However, if a student is under the age of six, they will be deemed eligible provided that they are eligible to

⁹² Tax Credit Scholarship for Low Income Students Act, 2014 Kan. Leg. Sess. 836 (codified as Kan.Stat. Ann. 72-4351 (amended by Ch. 95, 2017 Kan. Sess. Laws 1070 (codified as Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4351 effective July, 1 2018))).

⁹³ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4353(a) (West).

⁹⁴ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4357 (West)

⁹⁵ *Id.*

⁹⁶ *Id.*

⁹⁷ *Id.*

⁹⁸ *Id.*

⁹⁹ See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(d)(1)(A) (West)(requiring an eligible student to be an “at-risk student”); Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-5132(c)(1)(defining an “at-risk student” as a student who is eligible for free meals under the national school lunch act).

¹⁰⁰ See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(d)(1)(A) (West)(requiring that eligible students are “attending a public school”); Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(g) (West)(defining public school as a school that is operated by a school district and is identified by the state board as one of the lowest 100 performing schools).

¹⁰¹ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(d)(3)(A) (West).

be enrolled in a public school.¹⁰² Once a student is deemed an “eligible student”, they remain eligible to receive a scholarship until they either graduate high school or reach the age of 21.¹⁰³

While the statute requires eligible students to have been enrolled in a public school during the school year prior to the year a student wishes to receive a scholarship, it does not specify the length of time.¹⁰⁴ It is possible that students who attend private schools could enroll in a public school at the very end of a school year, and despite the short period of time in a public school, such students could potentially receive a scholarship to attend a participating private school the next school year.¹⁰⁵ Many other programs and proposed programs contain explicit language that prohibits those types of practices or set an exact minimum time period for their prior public-school enrollment requirement.¹⁰⁶ A previous version of the Georgia program contained similarly imprecise language, requiring only prior public-school enrollment.¹⁰⁷ Under that version of the Georgia program, private school students who went through the motions of enrolling in a public school, but did not ever attend the public school, were instantly qualified to receive a scholarship.¹⁰⁸ The “loophole” was likely an intended feature of the program by the drafters of the

¹⁰² Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(d)(3)(B) (West).

¹⁰³ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(d)(1)(B) (West).

¹⁰⁴ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352.

¹⁰⁵ See *supra* n. 104; *infra* n. 109.

¹⁰⁶ See *e.g.* Ga. Code. Ann. § 20-2A-1 (requiring eligible students to have been enrolled in a public school for at least 6 weeks); Ind. Code Ann. § 20-51-1-4.3 (West)(specifying that certain eligible students must have been enrolled in a public school in Indiana for at least “two semesters” immediately preceding the first semester for which the individual receives a choice scholarship).

¹⁰⁷ H.B. 773, 2008 Ga. Sess. Laws 1108 (codified as Ga. Code. Ann. § 20-2A-1 (amended by Act 335, 2013 Ga. Sess. Laws, 1061)(amending to require eligible students to be enrolled in Georgia public schools for at least six weeks))(defining eligible student as “a student who is a Georgia is resident enrolled in a Georgia secondary or primary public school).

¹⁰⁸ See Southern Education Foundation *supra* n. 88 at 14—17.

statute.¹⁰⁹ It is not clear whether the Kansas language is mere oversight, or if it too was meant to create a loophole.¹¹⁰

The maximum scholarship available to students under the program is \$8,000.¹¹¹ No minimum scholarship value is specified by the statute.¹¹² The discretion of SGOs in determining the scholarship value of awards granted to individual students is subject to few limitations. For example, unlike some other programs, SGOs are not required to reference a student’s household income when determining scholarship value.¹¹³ The maximum scholarship value is higher than the “Base State Aid Per-Pupil” or “Base Aid for Student Excellence” (BSAPP or BASE) and General Fund Aid per-pupil.¹¹⁴ The legislature’s most recent attempt at producing a constitutional funding formula set base state aid at \$4,000 per pupil.¹¹⁵ While General Fund Total Aid per-pupil was around \$ 6,840 for the 2017-18 school year.¹¹⁶

SGOs are subject to few regulations by the program.¹¹⁷ The program requires SGOs to maintain non-profit status.¹¹⁸ SGOs must spend 90% of contributions on scholarship awards.¹¹⁹

¹⁰⁹ *Id.*

¹¹⁰ There is very little information on students participating in the program. See Kansas State Department of Education School Finance Team, *Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarship Program Legislative Report for January 2018*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (2018), <http://www.ksde.org/Portals/0/School%20Finance/Action%20Items/Legislative%20Report%20January%202018%20%20TCLISSP.pdf>.

¹¹¹ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4353(e) (West).

¹¹² *Id.*

¹¹³ See e.g. 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/40 (West)(requiring SGOs to determine scholarship values with reference to eligible students’ household income).; See also Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354 (West)(containing no provisions to guide SGOs in determining individual scholarship value).

¹¹⁴ See *infra* n. 115 & 116.

¹¹⁵ See *Gannon v. State*, 402 P.3d 513, 522 (Kan. 2017); Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-5132 (West)(listing BASE aid as \$4,006 for the 2017-18 school year).

¹¹⁶ For the 2017-18 school year, General Fund Aid Total was \$ 3,275,373,608 and Full Time Enrolment (FTE) was 478.890. See KSDE, *General State Aid/Supplemental General State Aid for Kansas USDs 2017-2018*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, available at <https://zenodo.org/record/1170511/files/State%20aid%20per%20pupil.pdf>. See also http://budget.ks.gov/publications/FY2018/FY2018_Comparison_Report--8-4-2017.pdf (listing total expenditures for FY 2018 at \$ 3.1338 billion);

¹¹⁷ See e.g. Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354 (West)(regulating SGOs).

¹¹⁸ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(a)(3) (West).

¹¹⁹ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(c) (West).

When SGOs receive more than \$50,000 in contributions, they must file a surety bond payable to the state board for the amount equal to total contributions expected to be received for that year, or otherwise demonstrate the SGOs ability to pay an amount equal to expected contributions.¹²⁰ Additionally, SGOs are required to provide annual reports containing little valuable information, to the state board.¹²¹ Other minor regulations include a prohibition against providing scholarships to students from contributions made by a student’s relative.¹²² While SGOs are prohibited from accepting contributions with the express or implied condition that the contribution be used toward a scholarship for a particular student, there is no prohibition against “suggestions” that contributions be used for a particular student.¹²³ Nor is there a prohibition against accepting funds on the condition that they go to a particular school.¹²⁴ Notably, SGOs are allowed to limit scholarships to a single school or a particular type of school, provided they inform the state board in writing.¹²⁵

Private schools that participate in the program are subject to few regulations.¹²⁶ Initially, private schools participating in the program were not required to be accredited.¹²⁷ However, a 2017 amendment to the statute, that goes into effect in July 2018, requires participating private schools

¹²⁰ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(a)(5) (West)

¹²¹ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(f) (West)(requiring SGOs to submit a report containing the name and address of the SGO, the name and address of each eligible student with respect to whom an educational scholarship was awarded by the SGO, the total number and total dollar amount of contribution received during the 12 month reporting period, the total number and total dollar amount of educational scholarships awarded during the 12-month reporting period, and the total number and total dollar amount of educational scholarships awarded during the 12 month reporting period with respect to eligible students who qualified for the program by meeting the definition of “eligible student”).

¹²² Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(g)(1) (West).

¹²³ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(g)(2) (West). *See also* Ariz. Rev. Stat. § 43-1603 (permitting SGOs to allow donors to recommend student beneficiaries, but does not allow the organizations to “award, designate, or reserve scholarships *solely*” on the basis of the recommendation). *Emphasis added.*

¹²⁴ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354 (West).

¹²⁵ Kan. Stat. Ann. 72-4354(a)(8) (West).

¹²⁶ To participate in the program, a private school is merely required to notify the state board of its intention to participate. *See* Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(h) (West).

¹²⁷ *Supra* n. 93.

to be accredited by 2020.¹²⁸ Accreditation can be gained through the state board or through a number of regional and national accreditation associations.¹²⁹ Unlike some other programs, there is no requirement that participating private schools administer assessment tests for scholarship receiving students.¹³⁰ Private schools are not subject to any provisions that explicitly prohibit discrimination.¹³¹

III. An Analysis of the Kansas Program

This section lays out the argument that the program results in diminished democratic control over school policies, is likely to provide many if not most of the program benefits to high and middle-income households, and is likely to distribute program benefits on the basis of social group membership. Thus, the program is unlikely to be a viable strategy for addressing inequity within the Kansas system of public education. Although the program is

¹²⁸ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352(h) (West)(providing that “on or after July 1, 2020, a qualified school shall be accredited by the state board or a national or regional accrediting agency that is recognized by the state board for the purpose of satisfying the teaching performance assessment for professional licensure”).

¹²⁹ *Id.*

¹³⁰ *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/50(2)(B) (requiring participating private schools to administer assessments “in the same manner in which they are administered in public schools”). *See also* Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352 (providing no testing requirements).

¹³¹ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352 (West)(providing no provisions regarding discrimination by private schools).

currently limited in size,¹³² politicians have continuously campaigned to expand the program,¹³³ and such campaigns are likely to continue in the future.¹³⁴

a. The Kansas Program Diminishes Democratic Control Over Public Education Policy

The program partially privatizes the policymaking process that determines how public funds are distributed for educational purposes by giving immense decision-making powers to SGOs and participant taxpayers in determining how funds they receive and contribute are utilized.¹³⁵ Furthermore, the use of a tax credit ties ability to participate in the policymaking process to wealth and income.¹³⁶ The high cap on tax credits that individual taxpayers can claim under the program results in inequality in ability to participate in the policymaking process to be especially pronounced.¹³⁷ Even taxpayers who desire and have the ability to participate in the program through small donations may have their “voice” drowned out by the voice of taxpayers with the desire and ability to donate large sums of money.¹³⁸ Additionally, the program allows for decision-

¹³² See Kansas State Department of Education School Finance Team, *Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarship Program Legislative Report for January 2018*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (2018), <http://www.ksde.org/Portals/0/School%20Finance/Action%20Items/Legislative%20Report%20January%202018%20%20TCLISSP.pdf>.

¹³³ See e.g. Jonathan Shorman, *Measure to Expand Kansas Private School Tuition Tax Credits Provokes Controversy*, TOPEKA CAPITAL J., Feb. 2, 2016, <http://www.cjonline.com/news/2016-02-02/measure-expand-kansas-private-school-tuition-tax-credits-provokes-controversy>; 2017 Kansas House Bill No. 2374, Kansas Eighty-Seventh Legislature 2017 Regular Session (proposing an expansion to the program); Sam Brownback, *2017 State of the State Address*, GOVERNOR OF THE STATE OF KANSAS, Jan. 10, 2017;

¹³⁴ Many groups desire expansion of the program. See Kansas Catholic Conference, *Pro-“Choice”...Except When it Comes to Education*, KANSAS CATHOLIC CONFERENCE, Aug. 27, 2017, <http://www.ksathconf.org/2017/04/27/pro-choice-except-when-it-comes-to-education/>.

¹³⁵ Welner *supra* n. 53 at 6 (noting that under tax credit scholarship programs “control over funding decisions is largely delegated” to taxpayer-donors and SGOs).

¹³⁶ *Id.* at (Ch. 6)(noting that as result of the use of tax credits, “wealthier taxpayers have effective control over which schools- and to some extent, which families- receive” funding).

¹³⁷ *Id.* at (ch. 7)(noting that low level caps would “limit the disproportionate influence exercised by the wealthiest taxpayers”).

¹³⁸ Welner *infra* n. 137 (noting that wealth determines the amount of “votes” a taxpayer-policymaker has under the privatized policymaking process found in tax credit scholarship programs).

making power over the distribution of program funds to become concentrated in the hands of as few as 20 high-income taxpayers.¹³⁹ Further, participating taxpayer-policymakers are shielded from public scrutiny for their decisions, since the recipients of tax credits are kept confidential under Kansas laws and regulations.¹⁴⁰ Thus, taxpayers are totally unable to apply public pressure or make appeals to taxpayer-policymakers, no matter how great the taxpayers influence or how undesirable the taxpayer’s policies are.¹⁴¹ In essence, the program replaces a democratic system of policymaking with a plutocratic one.¹⁴²

The policymaking process determining school-level policies can also be characterized as plutocratic¹⁴³. School level policies are also privatized by the program. For example, private schools under the program are subject to very few limitations providing for public oversight or accountability.¹⁴⁴ Furthermore, school level policymakers cannot be held accountable through mechanisms of democratic control such as school board elections.¹⁴⁵ The decision-making process of private schools is further shielded from public oversight and accountability, since there is no

¹³⁹ 20 donors claiming the maximum credit available to individual taxpayers would claim all available tax credits under the program. *See* Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4357 (West).

¹⁴⁰ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 79-3234 (West)(providing that “it shall be unlawful” for state officials or employees “to make known in any way” any “particulars set forth or disclosed in any report, return, federal return, or federal return information” required under the act governing income taxation in the state”); XXIII Kan. Op. Atty. Gen. 15 (1989)(explaining that the statute prohibits the disclosure of “income or any particulars provided in state or federal income tax returns”). The confidentiality of tax credit recipients under Kansas laws can be contrasted with Missouri law, which provides mechanisms that the identities make tax credit recipients easily ascertainable by the public. *See* Mo. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 135.805 (West)(requiring the department of economic development to make information available for public inspection through the department’s website and the Missouri Accountability Portal).

¹⁴¹ Unlike in Missouri, where taxpayers are subject to public accountability through the Missouri Accountability Portal. *Id.*

¹⁴² *See* Welner *supra* n. 54 at 94 (noting that tax credit scholarship programs result in a “caricature of direct democracy-with the wealthy entitled to more votes”).

¹⁴³ School level policies also plutocratic

¹⁴⁴ *See* Robinson *supra* n. 75 at 260 (noting that tax credit scholarship programs, by design, subject private schools to very little government regulation, accountability or oversight); Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-XXXX (providing almost no accountability or oversight measures on participating private schools).

¹⁴⁵ *See* Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 25-2001 to -2024 (West)(codifying the “School Election Act” which requires school districts to hold nonpartisan elections).

requirement for something akin to school board meetings.¹⁴⁶ Further, ability to participate in policymaking at the school level is tied to wealth. For example, since taxpayers donate money to SGOs, who in turn allocate funding to private schools, both taxpayers and SGOs potentially have the ability to exercise immense influence over the operation of private schools.¹⁴⁷ Students able to pay full tuition, or students who can make up the difference between the scholarship value and the cost of full tuition, are more likely to be able to influence school officials compared to students who rely solely on financial aid and thus do not bring additional funding to the school.¹⁴⁸ Therefore, low income students and high-cost students, who provide less marginal funding¹⁴⁹, are unlikely to exercise as much influence on policy.¹⁵⁰ Compared to high-income and low-cost students. Students who can provide resources in addition to funding equal to full tuition are likely able to exercise the greatest influence on policy. However, in the end, no student is guaranteed recourse if they are unhappy with private school policies.

¹⁴⁶ See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 75-438 (West)(requiring that “all meetings for the conduct of the affairs of, and the transaction of business by, all legislative and administrative bodies and agencies of the state and political and taxing subdivisions” of the state “receiving or expending and supported in whole or in part by public funds shall be open to the public and no binding action by such public bodies or agencies shall be by secret ballot”); Kan. Stat. Ann. 75-4319 (West)(prohibiting bodies and agencies subject to the open meetings act from taking binding action during a closed meeting). Although participating schools receiving funds through the program receive public funds through tax expenditures, it is unlikely that the law would be interpreted to require open meetings for participating private schools. See *Kotterman v. Killian*, 972 P.2d 606 (holding that tax credits do not constitute “public money”).

¹⁴⁷Through their control over the distribution of program funds, SGOs and taxpayers may be able to influence school-level policies. See Welner, *supra* n. 127 & 128.

¹⁴⁸ See *Id.* (noting that the supply of families “with the financial means to afford the tuition payment above the voucher amount” act to increase demand and bring greater resources to private schools); *Id.* (noting that private schools “cannot be weighed down with students who pay little”).

¹⁴⁹ For example, a higher cost student who provides funding equal to the full cost of tuition would provide less marginal funding, as measured by funds provided minus cost of educating ($MF = F - C$), compared to a student who costs less to educate and who provides funding equal to the full cost of tuition.

¹⁵⁰ See also Welner *supra* n. 54 at 88 (noting that the supply of students who are less costly to educate effects resources available to private schools) *Id.* (noting that private schools cannot afford to be “weighed down” by students who cost too much to educate).

The program does not provide public control over policies through the market effects of consumer demand.¹⁵¹ Unlike traditional voucher programs, where parental choice effects policies through the distributional effect of choosing to apply a voucher, and thus funding, to a particular school, the Kansas program is totally unresponsive to parental choice.¹⁵² Theoretically, schools and closely affiliated SGOs¹⁵³ may have an incentive to limit their acceptance of eligible students, so as to increase funding per-pupil made available to the school.¹⁵⁴ Even if this is not the case, schools have no incentive to attract a large number of students, since the number of scholarship recipients attending a school does not determine the size of the subsidy the school receives through the program.¹⁵⁵ The only “competition” created by the program is the competition between SGOs and their affiliated schools to attract taxpayer donations.¹⁵⁶

b. The Program May Primarily Benefit High and Middle-Income Students at the Expense of Low-Income Students

¹⁵¹ Resources are allocated in accordance with taxpayer-donor preferences, not student preferences. *See See Sugarman supra* n. 55 at 18 (2014)(noting that SGOs compete with each other to attract donors). While SGOs have been suggested as a means to “put families on an equal footing” by “not having to compete for the patronage of individual taxpayer donors”. *Id.* at 18--9. However, it is not clear how this works without additional regulations on SGOs, especially when SGOs can limit scholarship grants to a particular school or type of school and taxpayers have complete discretion in choosing among SGOs. *See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(a)(8)* (West)(allowing for SGOs to limit schools or type of schools they will distribute funds to under the program).

¹⁵² ROBERT A. FOX & NINA K. BUCHANAN, *THE WILEY HANDBOOK OF SCHOOL CHOICE*, 288 (2017)(explaining how, in theory, school voucher programs act to distribute resources in reference to parental preferences).

¹⁵³ Under the Kansas program, SGOs can be set up for the sole purpose of supporting a single affiliated school. *See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4354(a)(8)* (West). Such SGOs have already operated under the Kansas program. *See Kansas State Department of Education School Finance Team, Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarship Program Legislative Report for January 2018*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (2018), <http://www.ksde.org/Portals/0/School%20Finance/Action%20Items/Legislative%20Report%20January%202018%20%20TCLISSP.pdf> (listing SGOs and their affiliated schools).

¹⁵⁴ Welner *supra* n. 54 at 88 (noting that schools have a financial incentive to “compete using selective criteria, that is limit low paying and high-cost students who do not provide marginal benefits to the school.”).

¹⁵⁵ The level of funding SGOs receive is determined by taxpayer-donors. *See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4353* (West)(providing for taxpayer-donors to participate in the program only through their interaction with SGOs, without reference to student demand for schools supported by the SGOs). *See also Welner, supra* n. 127.

¹⁵⁶ *See Sugarman supra* n. 55 at 18.

First, since ability to participate in policymaking is linked to wealth, policies produced under the program are likely to favor wealthy households rather than the general public. The program itself acts to subsidize private schools for all attending students, not just students participating in the program. Since students enrolled in private schools tend to be from higher-income households, the subsidization of private schools with public monies could primarily benefit students from higher income households.

Households with higher income, more education, and more active parents are more likely to participate in any choice program in general.¹⁵⁷ This is true even if the program is means tested, as the most well-off households in the eligible subpopulation are most likely to participate.¹⁵⁸ Under the Kansas program, households that in most contexts are considered middle-income are eligible to receive grants.¹⁵⁹ In fact, if the income requirement was the only criteria for eligibility, 40% of all students would qualify.¹⁶⁰ The Kansas program amplifies the general tendency of greater participation among higher income households, since scholarships do not have to cover full tuition costs.¹⁶¹ When the value of the scholarship is less than the full cost of tuition, only

¹⁵⁷ Welner *supra* n. 53.

¹⁵⁸ *Id.* at ch. 7 (noting that even in means tested programs, the highest educated, highest earning, and most active parents tend to participate in active choice programs much more than less well-off households);

¹⁵⁹ The Kansas program requires that students applying for a first-time scholarship be eligible for free school lunch. In Kansas, this means that for a student from a household of four to be eligible, the household income must not exceed \$45,510. See Department of Agriculture; Food and Nutrition Service Child Nutrition Programs Eligibility Guidelines, 82 Fed. Reg. 17182 (APR., 10, 2017). According to the Pew Research Foundation, middle-income households are households that earn between 60% and 200% of the median income for an area. See Richard Fry & Rakesh Kochhar, *Are You in the American Middle Class? Find Out With Our Income Calculator*, PEW RESEARCH CENTER, May 11, 2016, <http://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2016/05/11/are-you-in-the-american-middle-class/>. In Kansas the median income for a household is \$54,865. See *Median Household Income by State, 2009-2015*, UNIVERSITY OF KANSAS INSTITUTE FOR POLICY AND SOCIAL RESEARCH, available at <http://www.ipsr.ku.edu/ksdata/ksah/income/9inc1.pdf>. Thus, the range for middle-income runs between \$32,919 and \$109,730 for households in Kansas.

¹⁶⁰ *Expanding the Tax Credit Scholarships for Low Income Students Program: Hearing on H.B. 2374 Before the Kansas House Education Committee*, 2017 Legis. Sess. (Kan. 2017) (testimony of Mark Tallman Associate Executive Director for Advocacy for the Kansas Association of School Boards), available at <http://kasb.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/HB2374inHEd.pdf>.

¹⁶¹ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352 (West)(allowing for scholarships to cover only partial tuition)..

those families who can pay additional tuition will be able to participate.¹⁶² Furthermore, additional costs of private school attendance, such as uniforms, textbooks, and transportation, may prevent lower income households from participating, even if given full scholarships.¹⁶³ The tax credit scholarship program could entice middle class families to move into the attendance boundaries of low performing schools¹⁶⁴, however it is unlikely to provide students from low-income households with a significant increase in school choices available.¹⁶⁵

The program could also distribute scholarships to students from high-income households, even if household income greatly exceeds the programs' requirements.¹⁶⁶ Although eligibility initially requires the students to be fall under the definition of an "at-risk" student, continued participation does not.¹⁶⁷ Thus, as long as a student received funding under the program in the past, they are eligible to continue to receive program funds even if their household's income increases significantly.¹⁶⁸

While lower-income households may be unable to participate in the program, the public schools they utilize will likely be harmed by the program.¹⁶⁹ When students switch from public to

¹⁶² See e.g. Camille Phillips, *Middle-class Families Most Likely to Benefit from Illinois Tax Credit Scholarships*, *Expert Says*, ST. LOUIS PUBLIC RADIO, Sept. 22, 2017, <http://news.stlpublicradio.org/post/middle-class-families-most-likely-benefit-illinois-tax-credit-scholarships-expert-says> (discussing a similar Illinois program and noting that students from middle income households who can afford to pay extra tuition will be able to utilize scholarships even if they cover only the partial cost of tuition).

¹⁶³ See e.g. *supra* n. 155.

¹⁶⁴ The program could attract Middle Class families to central cities since it subsidizes their continued attendance at schools segregated by class and race. This has even been seen as a beneficial feature of tax credit scholarship programs. See Nicole Stelle Garnett, *Affordable Private Education and the Middle Class City*, 77 U. Chi. L. Rev. 201 (2010).

¹⁶⁵ *Who Gains Most from School Choice? Not Low-Income Students of Color*, EDUCATION OPPORTUNITY NETWORK, <http://educationopportunitynetwork.org/who-gains-from-school-choice-not-low-income-students-of-color/> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018).

¹⁶⁶ See *infra* n. 162.

¹⁶⁷ Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352 (West).

¹⁶⁸ *Id.*

¹⁶⁹ Welner, *supra* n. 53 (explaining that, even within a means tested program, "the wealthiest, best educated, and most involved" parents are more likely to exercise choice, and that as they exit the public school system students in public schools are further disadvantaged).

private school using program scholarships, funding is diverted from public schools to private schools.¹⁷⁰ The public school's fixed costs per student goes up in such circumstances, leaving less funds per student for other expenses like classroom material or tutor programs.¹⁷¹ If a public school has stable or falling enrollment levels, rather than rising enrollment levels, they can be significantly harmed by the loss of students who participate in the program.¹⁷² Additionally, the parents who provide the most support for public schools are also the most likely to utilize choice.¹⁷³ This may harm public schools by removing these parents, and their social and political capital, from the public school system.¹⁷⁴

c. May Primarily Benefit Only Certain Social Groups

The program may increase social polarization and inequity by distributing program benefits to students based on a student's membership to a particular social group. Schools could possibly practice a variety of forms of de jure discrimination.¹⁷⁵ Unlike some other programs, the Kansas program does not explicitly prohibit SGOs or private schools from practicing any type of discrimination when determining whether to accept a student's application to attend the school or

¹⁷⁰ Kansas state aid to public schools has been determined in reference to "Weighted Full Time Enrollment". As enrollment drops, so does Full Time Enrollment. This causes funding allocated to the school to decrease. *SEE*

¹⁷¹ *See Scholarship Tax Credits*, NATIONAL CONFERENCE OF STATE LEGISLATURES, <http://www.ncsl.org/research/education/school-choice-scholarship-tax-credits.aspx> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018)(noting that opponents criticize program because it hurts public schools by raising fixed facility costs per student).

¹⁷² Welner *supra* n. 54 at 73 (explaining that as students exit public school districts schools may have to close and would likely result in loss of efficiencies of scale).

¹⁷³ Osamudia R. James, *Opt-Out Education: School Choice As Racial Subordination*, 99 Iowa L. Rev. 1083, 1105 (2014)(explaining that the loss of "education connoisseurs" voices will harm poor and minority school districts most in need of this economic and social capital").

¹⁷⁴ Raquel Aldana, *When the Free-Market Visits Public Schools: Answering the Roll Call for Disadvantaged Students*, 15 Natl. Black L.J. 26, 31 (1998)(explaining that school choice policies can create "pockets of failure", in part because the students left behind may have parents who are less involved or less informed).

¹⁷⁵ Tax credit scholarship programs may result in de jure or de facto discrimination by SGOs. Regulations could be implemented to prevent such discrimination within tax credit scholarship programs. *See Sugarman supra* n. 55 at 20(noting that programs should take steps to prevent the practice of de jure discrimination on the part of SGOs in their allocation of funds to schools and families); Welner *supra* n. 53 at 185 (advocating the necessity of such provisions in tax credit scholarship programs that seek to be equitable). Kansas does not contain such a provision requiring the practice of non-discrimination by participating by private schools. *See Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-4351 to -4357* (West).

in determining how much in scholarship funding to provide to a student.¹⁷⁶ In practice, SGOs are already prohibited from providing scholarships to schools with racially discriminatory policies.¹⁷⁷ However, discrimination along other lines such as religious beliefs, familial status, disability, or sexual orientation are not prohibited by federal laws, and thus may be practiced by schools participating in the Kansas program without fear of consequence. Many qualified private schools are religious in nature, and some have already adopted religiously discriminatory policies absent regulation prohibiting such practices.¹⁷⁸

Even if schools themselves do not have racially discriminatory policies, the preferences of parents could lead to de facto racial segregation under such programs.¹⁷⁹ Furthermore, since religious organizations tend to be racially segregated, de facto discrimination could occur due to the affiliation of SGOs and private schools with particular religious institutions or organizations.¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁶ For example, the Arizona tax credit scholarship program explicitly prohibits participating private schools from discriminating on the basis of race, color, disability, national origin, or familial status. *See* Ariz. Rev. Stat. Ann. §§15-891–891.06 (West). The Kansas law contains no such provision. *See* Kan. Stat. Ann. §§ 72-4351 to -4357 (West).

¹⁷⁷ The Kansas program requires SGOs have tax exempt status under IRS Section 501(3)(c). *See* KSA 72-4354(a)(3) (West)(requiring SGOs to have tax exempt status under 501(3)(c)). *See also* IRS Section 501(3)(c). Private schools that do not have a racially nondiscriminatory policy as to students do not qualify for tax exempt status under 501(c)(3). *See* Rev. Ru. 71-447, 1971-2 C.B. 230 (IRS RRU 1971); *Bob Jones U. v. U.S.*, 461 U.S. 575, 575 (1983). Scholarship granting organizations that provided scholarships to schools with racially discriminatory policies would likely not qualify for tax exempt status under 501(c)(3), since it is unlikely they would be found “charitable under Rev. Rul. 71-447, 1971-2 C.B. 230. *See* IRS, 1985 *Continuing Professional Education: J. Activities that are Illegal or Contrary to Public Policy*, INTERNAL REVENUE SERVICE, <https://www.irs.gov/pub/irs-tege/eotopicj85.pdf> (discussing how the rule would be applied to scholarship trusts).

¹⁷⁸ . *See* Sugarman *supra* n. 55 at 20 (noting that regulations need to be incorporated into tax credit scholarship programs, in order to prevent de jure and de facto discrimination by school; Welner *supra* n. 53 at 185 (proposing that anti-discrimination provisions be included in such programs since qualified schools are otherwise likely to practice discrimination).

¹⁷⁹ *See e.g.* Welner *supra* n. 53 at 24 (discussing racial segregation that often results from choice programs).

¹⁸⁰ *See e.g.* Michael Lipka, *Many U.S. Congregations are Still Racially Segregated, but Things are Changing*, PEW RESEARCH CENTER, Dec. 8, 2014, <http://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2014/12/08/many-u-s-congregations-are-still-racially-segregated-but-things-are-changing-2/>; Diana Jean Schemo, *Study Finds Church Schools Racially Segregated*, N.Y. TIMES, June 27, 2002, <http://www.nytimes.com/2002/06/27/us/study-finds-church-schools-racially-segregated.html> (noting that private religious schools, particularly Roman Catholic ones, are more racially segregated than public schools). The more religious affiliation influences students and their parents school choice, the more intense the segregate tendencies of vouchers will be. Robert K. Vischer, *Racial Segregation in American Churches and its Implications for School Vouchers*, 53 Fla L. Rev. 193, 223 (2001). Since religious affiliation is used by some qualified schools to determine whether a student will be admitted to a school or whether a student will pay a higher

If participating schools that are affiliated with organizations that predominately or disproportionately serve a single racial group, then program benefits are likely to be disproportionately distributed primarily to that racial group.¹⁸¹ Thus, even where scholarships are distributed on the basis of religious affiliation alone, racial segregation is a likely result.

Discrimination on the basis religious affiliation appears to be common under the program. Some Christian schools that participate in the Kansas program require church membership in order for a student to enroll the school.¹⁸² Other participating schools provide a tuition discount to students whose households belong to the church.¹⁸³ Since scholarships do not have to cover the full cost of tuition, these options are much more affordable to church members and may effectively exclude non-members from benefiting from the program.¹⁸⁴ Additionally, SGOs may market the

tuition rate, religious affiliation is likely very influential to choices made by families that participate in the program. *See supra* n. 176 & 177.

¹⁸¹ The Kansas program likely benefits schools that disproportionately serve students of a particular race. For example, Catholic schools that participate in the program tend to serve a higher percentage of white students and a much lower percentage of Black students relative to the racial composition of the community. For example, in the 2017-18 school year only around 2% of the student population in schools operated by the Kansas City Catholic Diocese was Black. *See* KSDE Data Central, *2017-2018 State Headcount Enrollment by District, Grade, Race, and Gender (All Schools)*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (2018), available at https://zenodo.org/record/1170525/files/KSDE%20Data%20school%20racial%20compisition%202017_18.pdf. The Diocese operated schools in Topeka, Shawnee, Seneca, Roeland Park, Prarie Village, Paola, Overland Park, Ottawa, Olathe, Marysville, Lenexa, Leawood, Leavenworth, Kansas City, Emporia, Bucyrus, and Atchison. *See Find Your School*, ARCHDIOCESE OF KANSAS CITY IN KANSAS, <https://www.archkck.org/schools/find-your-school> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018). According to data from the 2010 Census, the Black population of these communities accounted for 10% of the total population. *See* U.S. Census (2010).

¹⁸² For example, Central Christian Academy, a “qualified school” in Wichita, requires both parents or gaurdians in a potential student’s home to give “clear testimony of faith in Jesus Christ” as part of its admissions process. Testimonies must be both written on the application and verbally shared in an admissions interview. Additionally, to gain admission, an applicant’s family is required to regularly attend and be actively involved in an “evangelical, Bible-centered church”. *See Admission Criteria*, CENTRAL CHRISTIAN ACADEMY (WICHITA, KANSAS), <http://www.ccalions.org/admission-criteria/> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018).

¹⁸³ For example, Christ the King Parish School in Kansas City, Kansas charges over \$1,500 more in yearly tuition to non-parishioners compared to parishioners. *See Admission*, CHRIST THE KING SCHOOL (KANSAS CITY, KANSAS), <https://ctkkck.eduk12.net/other?Item=Admissions> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018).

¹⁸⁴ *See* Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4352 (West)(allowing for scholarship values to be less than tuition and other costs).

scholarships only toward students belonging to an affiliated church, meaning that these families are potentially the only households with significant knowledge of the program.¹⁸⁵

Since schools and SGOs can refuse admission to students and distribute scholarship funds based on religious and ideological affiliation, the program promotes the sorting of students on the basis of religion or ideology.¹⁸⁶ This may lead to greater political polarization, as curricula may become more radical and politically or ideologically charged.¹⁸⁷ Additionally, allocating educational resources on the basis of religious or ideological affiliation will likely promote educational inequality.¹⁸⁸ Public schools are a physical and institutional manifestation of “we” and the shared interests of the People.¹⁸⁹ Public schools act as a unifying force on America’s increasingly diverse society.¹⁹⁰ Public schools have traditionally been a concern for all citizens,

¹⁸⁵ Sugarman *supra* n. 55 at 20 (noting that how SGOs make their available scholarships known to the community may result in de facto discrimination against students who do not belong to a religious institution that is affiliated with the SGO). See *Kansas Tax Credit Scholarship for Low Income Students Program*, CATHOLIC EDUCATION FOUNDATION OF KANSAS, <https://www.cefks.org/sites/default/files/pdf/school-website-office-copy.pdf> (providing an example of SGO marketing).

¹⁸⁶ See *supra* n. 177-79.

¹⁸⁷ For examples, some Christian school textbooks teach conceptions of American identity that are exclusionary and likely promote intolerance towards other racial, religious, or political groups. Bob Jones University Press and A Beka are two major publishers of such textbooks. See Frances R. A. Paterson, *Building a Conservative Base: Teaching History and Civics in Voucher Supported Schools*, PHI DELTA KAPPAN, Oct. 2000, at 150. A Beka and Bob Jones University Press textbooks are used by schools that participate in the Kansas program. See e.g. Overland Christian Schools, *Welcome to Overland Christian Schools*, OVERLAND CHRISTIAN SCHOOLS, http://overlandchristian.org/wp-content/uploads/2008/09/pr-booklet_web.pdf (last visited Feb. 8, 2018). Many of the program’s approved accrediting associations advertise Bob Jones University Press textbooks. See e.g. Association of Christian Teachers Schools: *Member Benefits*, ASSOCIATION OF CHRISTIAN TEACHERS AND SCHOOLS, <http://www.actsschools.org/Benefits.html> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018)(offering “Curriculum Discounts” on Bob Jones University Press textbooks). See also *Recognized National or Regional Accrediting Agencies*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION <http://www.ksde.org/Agency/Division-of-Learning-Services/Teacher-Licensure-and-Accreditation/Licensure/Recognized-K-12-Accrediting-Agencies> (last visited Feb. 8, 2018).

¹⁸⁸ MARTHA MINOW, IN BROWN’S WAKE: LEGACIES OF AMERICA’S EDUCATIONAL LANDMARK, 135 (2010).

¹⁸⁹ Martha Minow, *Choice or Commonality: Welfare and Schooling After the End of Welfare As We Knew It*, 49 DUKE L.J. 493, 495 (1999)(noting that school choice risks “diminishing the sense of “we”, the collective to which everyone in the country should feel connected or responsible”).

¹⁹⁰ See Joel Kotkin, *The Changing Demographics of America: The United States Population Will Expand by 100 Million Over the Next 40 Years. Is This a Reason to Worry?*, SMITHSONIAN MAGAZINE, Aug. 2010 (explaining how the declining birthrates in the American born population, coupled with relatively high rates of immigration, is rapidly changing the demographics of the United States); Minow *supra* n. 184 at 496.

even for those who did not utilize them.¹⁹¹ Further, like the current jurisdictional fragmentation of school districts, fragmentation of the school system along social¹⁹² and ideological¹⁹³ grounds will likely lead to greater polarization.¹⁹⁴ Politically polarized social groups, sorted into separate homogenous schools, are unlikely to share educational resources in an equitable manner.¹⁹⁵

Since taxpayer and SGO policymaking determine the distribution of funds, students who desire a school that taxpayers and SGOs have not supported will not benefit from the program.¹⁹⁶ The options for a religious education through the program are limited to those groups who can attract taxpayer or SGO funding.¹⁹⁷ This may result in wealthier and higher population religious

¹⁹¹ Minow *supra* n. 184 at 496.

¹⁹² Of course, public schools already tend to be segregated by social group (i.e. race or socioeconomic status). However, segregation by social group is somewhat constrained since it technically operates on the basis of political geography. A household with sufficient resources could most likely move to nearly any school district in the county. However, regardless of the amount of resources they possess, a family that practices Catholicism, Judaism, Islam, or other religion could not send their children to a school like Central Christian Academy in Wichita. *Supra* n. 177.

¹⁹³ BENJAMIN JUSTICE & COLIN MACLEOD, HAVE A LITTLE FAITH: RELIGION, DEMOCRACY AND THE AMERICAN PUBLIC SCHOOL, 140 (discussing curriculum, published by Accelerated Christian Education, that included materials that teach that racial segregation is desirable and that homosexuality is a learned behavior); ALAN WOLFE, SCHOOL CHOICE THE MORAL DEBATE, 150 (2009)(discussing how religious private schools may teach intolerance and promote a repressive understanding of “the good life”); PATRICK J. WOLF & STEPHEN MACEDO, EDUCATING CITIZENS: INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVES ON CIVIC VALUES AND SCHOOL CHOICE, 372 (2004)(noting that a positive civic orientation may not endure in schools of choice without strong safeguards). Mark Gradstein & Moshe Justman, *The Melting Pot and School Choice*, 89 JOURNAL OF PUBLIC ECONOMICS 871, 872 (noting that social polarization may increase under voucher programs if the content of private schools’ curriculum is not properly regulated).

¹⁹⁴ *Supra* n. 184 & 185.

¹⁹⁵ Along the lines of the fragmentation analogy above, populations that utilize suburban school districts tend to be more politically powerful than those utilizing urban school districts, and their relative political influence has usually resulted in public policy that acts to concentrate educational resources in suburban school districts. See SCOTT M. ROULIER, SHAPING AMERICAN DEMOCRACY: LANDSCAPES AND URBAN DESIGN (2017)(noting the concentration of wealth in suburban areas and the resulting political influence of suburban populations); IAN SHAPIRO, ET AL, POLITICAL REPRESENTATION, 131 (noting that suburban whites have an interest in avoiding the sharing of educational resources, and instead try to avoid, rather than addressing, low performing urban school districts and the effects on the less economically advantaged populations they serve).

¹⁹⁶ See Kan. Stat. Ann. § 72-4353 (West)(giving taxpayer-donors the power to determine how funds are distributed between participating SGOs, regardless of student preferences for such education).

¹⁹⁷ SGOs could raise funds through solicitations, which would favor well resourced and organized SGOs who have the ability to market to wealthy individuals that approve of the SGOs mission. See Sugarman *supra* n. 55 at 19 (2014)(noting that SGOs could play an important role in soliciting donations). Since SGOs under the Kansas program tend to be affiliated with a particular religious sect, the ability to market and number of wealthy donors who agree with the school’s mission would likely be a function of that religious sect’s wealth. See Kansas State Department of Education School Finance Team, *Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarship Program Legislative Report for January 2018*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (2018),

groups receiving funding while less wealthy religious groups are forced to rely solely on private funding.¹⁹⁸ This seems to be the case in Kansas, where funds are primarily directed toward Catholic schools, instead of toward schools affiliated with, for example, Judaism or Islam.¹⁹⁹ A non-religious education is likely to be totally unavailable to families participating in the program.²⁰⁰ No such non-religious schools have received funding through the program.²⁰¹ Additionally, even maximum scholarships under the program do not cover the full cost of tuition at most of the state's non-religious schools.²⁰²

Finally, schools may have an incentive to not admit students from certain social groups based on the higher average cost of educating such students.²⁰³ For example, students who belong to certain cultural-linguistic groups may be unattractive to private schools if such students are not usually proficient in the English language.²⁰⁴

IV. Policy Alternatives

a. Reforming the Program?

<http://www.ksde.org/Portals/0/School%20Finance/Action%20Items/Legislative%20Report%20January%202018%20%20TCLISSP.pdf> (listing SGOs and their affiliated schools).

¹⁹⁸ See Welner *supra* n. 54 at 95 (noting that the private policymaking process embedded within tax credit scholarship programs results in the allocation of tax benefits to support those institutions that are most popular with the state's wealthiest residents).

¹⁹⁹ All SGOs that received funding for the 2017-18 school year were affiliated with religious, Christian and Catholic private schools. See Kansas State Department of Education School Finance Team, *Tax Credit for Low Income Students Scholarship Program Legislative Report for January 2018*, KANSAS STATE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION (2018),

<http://www.ksde.org/Portals/0/School%20Finance/Action%20Items/Legislative%20Report%20January%202018%20%20TCLISSP.pdf> (listing SGOs and their affiliated schools).

²⁰⁰ *Id.*

²⁰¹ *Id.*

²⁰² *Tuition and Fees 2017-2018*, TOPEKA COLLEGIATE SCHOOL, http://www.topekacollegiate.org/editoruploads/files/Tuition_and_Fees_2017-2018.pd (last visited Feb. 8, 2018).

²⁰³ See Welner *supra* n. 53.

²⁰⁴ See Sugarman *supra* n. 55 at 40 (2014) (noting that some private schools may be poorly staffed to deal with non-English speakers).

The more a program regulates participating schools, the less likely private schools will be willing to participate.²⁰⁵ If participating schools were required to admit all students like public schools are, it is likely that private schools would be less willing to participate.²⁰⁶ While requiring scholarship values to cover tuition would result in much fewer students receiving scholarships, and may result in less participating private schools.²⁰⁷ Many of these reforms would negate many of the supposed benefits that tax credit scholarship programs provide.²⁰⁸ However, tax credit scholarships are an effective policy for directing public educational resources and tax benefits to politically favored groups, if that is a goal policy makers desire.²⁰⁹

b. Other Forms of School Choice?

²⁰⁵ See e.g. *Robinson supra* n. 75 at 259–60 (2000)(noting that private school advocates are weary of “intrusive” government regulations).

²⁰⁶ See e.g. *Sugarman supra* n. 55 at 40 (2014)(noting that the more control schools retain over admissions, the more likely existing private schools will participate in the program and that private schools may be unwilling or unable to deal with certain high-needs students).

²⁰⁷ *Welner supra* n. 53.

²⁰⁸ See *Robinson supra* n. 200.

²⁰⁹ Political leaders view tax expenditures as a way to distribute public money to their favored constituencies or actives. See WELFARE FOR THE WEALTHY: PARTIES, SOCIAL SPENDING, AND INEQUALITY IN THE UNITED STATES. Tax expenditures subsidize private sector social goods or welfare, which primarily benefits the providers and recipients of the private welfare. See *Id.* Under progressive tax regimes, like the Kansas income tax, tax expenditures provide the largest financial benefits to citizens who make the most income. See *Id.* See also Kan. Stat. Ann. § 79-32, 110 (West)(establishing a progressive income tax). The Kansas program distributes money to Christian schools, providing benefits to the recipients of the program’s private-sector welfare benefits, which are Christian households and the welfare providers, which are Christian institutions. See *supra* n. 173. High income households or businesses and Christian households and organizations are major constituencies of the Republican party. See e.g. Pew Research Center, *Religious Landscape Study: Evangelical Protestants*, PEWFORUM.ORG, MAY 12, 2015, <http://www.pewforum.org/religious-landscape-study/religious-tradition/evangelical-protestant/> (showing that Evangelical Protestants tend to be affiliated with the Republican Party); Pew Research Center, *Intendents Take Center Stage in Obama Era: Party Affiliation and Composition*, PEOPLE-PRESS.ORG, May 21, 2009, <http://www.people-press.org/2009/05/21/section-1-party-affiliation-and-composition/> (noting that high income households tend to be affiliated with the Republican party). Catholics are less likely to identify as Republican compared to Evangelicals. See Pew Research Center, *Religious Landscape Study: Evangelical Protestants*, PEWFORUM.ORG, MAY 12, 2015, <http://www.pewforum.org/religious-landscape-study/religious-tradition/evangelical-protestant/>; Pew Research Center, *Religious Landscape Study: Catholics*, PEWFORUM.ORG, MAY 12, 2015, <http://www.pewforum.org/religious-landscape-study/religious-tradition/catholic/>. However, Catholics who utilize private schools are disproportionately Republican compared to the entire Catholic population. See S. J. Hughson, *CONNECTING JESUS TO SOCIAL JUSTICE: CATHOLIC CHRISTOLOGY AND PUBLIC THEOLOGY*, 66 (2013)(noting that Catholic Republicans attend Catholic schools more than Catholic Democrats).

School choice is likely ineffective at improving educational outcomes or equality of educational opportunity. The “choice” available under school choice programs is often “coerced” decision.²¹⁰ Students, disproportionately and in many areas mostly minority, are forced to choose between low performing public schools being drained of resources and whatever options are available under the school choice program.²¹¹ School choice programs shift the risk of school failure from society to individuals and families.²¹² In doing so, school choice programs allow for structural inequities to be ignored and go unaddressed.²¹³ Additionally, school choice programs may always result in stratification and inequities as the most effective advocates for public schools, higher educated parents and “education consumers”, are more likely to utilize choice.²¹⁴ Better educated and more socially connected parents are also more likely to make choose the best performing schools.²¹⁵ Thus, even when income is controlled for, choice is unlikely to contribute to an equitable public school system. Furthermore, school choice may contribute to polarization and discrimination by allowing social groups to segregate themselves into more socially and ideologically homogenous schools.²¹⁶

c. Strengthening the System of *Public* Schools

²¹⁰James *supra* n. 168 at 1085–88.

²¹¹ See e.g. Mark Dynarski, *On Negative Effects of vouchers*, BROOKINGS INSTITUTION, May 26 2016, <https://www.brookings.edu/research/on-negative-effects-of-vouchers/>.

²¹² See e.g. Minow *supra* n. 184 at 496 (noting that school choice allows “recipients and providers” to “retreat from a sense of the collective good” and may result in citizens coming “to see schooling and caring for the poor as outside their sphere of concern”).

²¹³ Osmaduia *supra* n. 187 at 1085.

²¹⁴ See James *supra* n. 168 at 1104-05 (noting that “marginalized minority parents” are less likely to have the necessary information for making wise school choices and that those students who do not exit are left behind in public schools, which are rapidly declining as a result of the exit of better educated and more socially connected families); Susan L. DeJarnatt, *School Choice and the (Ir)rational Parent*, 15 Geo. J. on Poverty L. & Policy 1, 8 (2008)(noting that decision making is effected by a decider’s social status and personal connections). .

²¹⁵ See James *supra* n. 209.

²¹⁶ See Minow *supra* n. 207 (noting the potential for school choice policies to cause “the retreat” of recipients and providers of schooling into homogeneous groups).

Looking to the ideologies of market fundamentalism²¹⁷ and consumerism²¹⁸ are unlikely to provide solutions that the system of *public* schools require.²¹⁹ At best, such policies could lead to slightly improved schools for *some* students.²²⁰ Due to America's ideological shift toward market fundamentalism and the embrace of neoliberal policies by the majority of politicians in both major political parties the school policy debate has shifted focus away from policies that can help improve the *public* schools for all students.²²¹ Perhaps the best policy to address inequities within the system of public education, would be to direct more resources to schools that are fully embedded within the system and that badly need such resources.²²² Reforms, such as changes to assessment testing, which could give teachers more flexibility in the classroom, could be effective at improving student outcomes.²²³ Other reforms, like greater regionalism in school district governance, could possibly allow for a more equitable allocation of resources across public schools, especially in metropolitan areas.²²⁴ Greater regional cooperation in affordable housing

²¹⁷ See FRED L. BLOCK, *THE POWER OF MARKET FUNDAMENTALISM* (2014)(defining market fundamentalism as the “quasi-religious certainty expressed by contemporary advocates of market self-regulation”). See also

²¹⁸ School choice, and the belief that parental choice is somehow a magic bullet, clearly reflects the major beliefs of consumerism. See e.g. JOEL SPRING, *EDUCATING THE CONSUMER-CITIZEN: A HISTORY OF THE MARRIAGE OF SCHOOLS, ADVERTISING, AND MEDIA* (2003)(noting that consumer ideology includes the beliefs that consumption of goods and services can transform one's life). Minow *supra* n. 207 (noting that school choice converts “public expenditures for public purposes into individualized consumer choices”).

²¹⁹ See CENTER FOR TAX AND BUDGET ACCOUNTABILITY, *ANALYSIS OF INDIANA SCHOOL CHOICE PROGRAM* (2015).

²²⁰ Welner *supra* n. 53.

²²¹ See *infra* n. 215.

²²² Increases in state funding to low-income school districts significantly improves performance in those districts and results in a narrowing of the gap between students from low-income and higher-income school districts. Bruce D Baker, *Evaluating the Recession's Impact on State School Finance Systems*, EDUCATION POLICY ANALYSIS ARCHIVES, Sept. 13, 2014.

²²³ See generally PENCILS DOWN: RETHINKING HIGH-STAKES TESTING AND ACCOUNTABILITY IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS (Wayne Au, Melissa Bollow Temple eds., 2012)(providing overview of problems associated with high stakes testing and suggesting possible reforms to make testing fairer and more accurate in terms of measuring student outcomes).

²²⁴ See generally Angela Glover Blackwell, *It Takes A Region*, 31 Fordham Urb. L.J. 1303, 1306 (2004)(discussing regionalism and the problems that are found in metropolitan areas that regionalism policies could address); See also Erika K. Wilson, *Toward A Theory of Equitable Federated Regionalism in Public Education*, 61 UCLA L. Rev. 1416, 1468–78 (2014)(proposing an “Equitable Federated Regionalism” framework to address problems in metropolitan area public education systems).

policy could also allow for more equity in public school systems.²²⁵ Additionally, “systems based”²²⁶ reforms, such as programs to build overall “teaching capacity”²²⁷ have been successful in other countries, and would likely be successful here too.²²⁸

V. Conclusion

Like many of the other states, the Kansas public-school system is plagued by structural inequities caused by historical and contemporary discriminatory policies. The Kansas Tax Credit Scholarship for Low Income Students Program is not a viable policy for promoting greater equity within the Kansas public school system. School choice policies in general are unlikely to lead to improved aggregate student outcomes or equality in educational opportunity. Markets, consumerism, and competition are great when applied in proper circumstances. The provision of the most important public good within our society is likely not a proper circumstance.²²⁹ Policies aimed at improving the state’s system of *public* schools should be pursued. Policies seeking to provide public education through stratified markets should be avoided. Instead, of creating quasi-public-school systems that exist side-by-side with the already existing public-school system, efforts at reform should be directed at the already established school system.

²²⁵ Martha Minow, *Confronting the Seduction of Choice: Law, Education, and American Pluralism*, 120 Yale L.J. 814, 846 (2011)(discussing the Gautreaux Assisted Housing program in the Chicago Metropolitan Area, which assisted low income families in moving to middle-class suburbs).

²²⁶ A systems-based approach aims to improve results across the entire system. On the other hand, school choice improves results only for those who exit the system and choose a high performing school. See <https://edsources.org/wp-content/uploads/old/Fullan-Wrong-Drivers11.pdf>;

²²⁷ *Id.*

²²⁸ *Id.*

²²⁹ See Aldana *supra* n. 169 at 36 (noting that “the market theory of school choice is in direct competition with educational equity”); Minow *supra* n. 207 (noting that a privatized education system is likely to be insufficient to “promote the public purposes of social cohesion, equal opportunity, and respect for religious and ethnic diversity”).

Appendix:**Recently Enacted Tax Credit Scholarship Program Laws)****I. Illinois (Enacted 2017)**

The Illinois program²³⁰ is called the “Invest in Kids Act”.²³¹ It was adopted during the 2017 legislative session.²³² The credit offered by the Illinois program is worth 75% of the donation value.²³³ The individual cap on credits is \$1,000,000.²³⁴ The total program cap on credits is \$75,000,000.²³⁵ Both businesses and individuals may claim the program’s tax credit.²³⁶ Taxpayers are prohibited from claiming a federal income tax deduction and the state tax credit for the same donation.²³⁷ Information about taxpayers claiming program credits may be made available to the public, provided that the information is aggregated in such a manner that information contained in any individual tax return is not disclosed.²³⁸ Credits must be awarded in a manner that is geographically proportionate to enrollment in recognized non-public schools.²³⁹ The program accomplishes this through the state board’s allocation of credits between five geographic regions in the state.²⁴⁰

²³⁰ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/1 to -40/999.

²³¹ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/1.

²³² EDUCATION—EVIDENCE-BASED SCHOOL FUNDING, 2017 Ill. Legis. Serv. P.A. 100-465 (S.B. 1947) (WEST).

²³³ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/10.

²³⁴ *Id.*

²³⁵ *Id.*

²³⁶ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/10.

²³⁷ *Id.*

²³⁸ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 5/917.

²³⁹ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/10.

²⁴⁰ Ill. Admin. Code. Tit. 86, § 1000 Illus. A.

To be eligible, a student's household income must not exceed 300% of the federal poverty level.²⁴¹ To remain eligible after initially receiving a scholarship, a student's household income must not exceed 400% of the federal poverty level.²⁴² Additionally, a student must be eligible to attend a public elementary or high school in Illinois in the semester immediately preceding the semester in which they first receive a scholarship.²⁴³ However, if a student is starting school in Illinois for the first time, they do not have to meet this requirement.²⁴⁴

Under the Illinois program, SGOs are called "scholarship granting organization".²⁴⁵ SGOs must spend at least 95% of donations received on scholarships.²⁴⁶ SGOs are subject to a variety of regulations.²⁴⁷ SGOs and taxpayers are somewhat limited in their ability to direct funds to particular schools or students.²⁴⁸ While corporate, business, and trusts are not allowed to direct donations to a particular school or subset of schools, individual donors are allowed to direct donations to particular schools and subsets of schools.²⁴⁹

There is also a provision in the statutes that explicitly requires SGOs to comply with the anti-discrimination provisions of 42 U.S.C. 200d.²⁵⁰ However, 42 U.S.C 200d merely prohibits discrimination on the basis of "race, color, or national origin",²⁵¹ which is already a de-facto prohibition on SGOs since they must be 501(c)(3) non-profits.²⁵² Additionally, SGOs are required to make annual reports containing a copy of their financial statements and evidence that the SGO

²⁴¹ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5.

²⁴² *Id.*

²⁴³ *Id.*

²⁴⁴ *Id.*

²⁴⁵ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5.

²⁴⁶ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5.

²⁴⁷ *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/15.

²⁴⁸ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/10.

²⁴⁹ *Id.*

²⁵⁰ *Id.*

²⁵¹ 42 U.S.C.A. § 2000d (West).

²⁵² 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5; *supra* n. 178.

has complied with the program's requirements.²⁵³ Annual reports are also required to include demographic information on students the SGO granted scholarships to.²⁵⁴

Furthermore, SGOs are subject to regulations restricting their discretion over the granting of scholarships.²⁵⁵ SGOs must allow eligible students to attend any qualified school of the student's choosing.²⁵⁶ SGOs are also required to give priority to students who received a scholarship from the SGO in the previous years²⁵⁷, to eligible students from households with income that is less than 185% of the federal poverty level²⁵⁸, students who reside within a "focus district"²⁵⁹, and students who are siblings of students currently receiving a scholarship.²⁶⁰

Scholarship value must not exceed the lesser of statewide public-school average operational expense per student (public school expenses per-student) or the necessary costs and fees for attendance at the qualified school where the scholarship is to be applied.²⁶¹ Additionally, scholarships must be "pro-rated", or cover a certain percentage of tuition, depending on student household income.²⁶² For an eligible student whose household income is less than 185% of the federal poverty level, the scholarship amount must be 100% of costs and fees if less than public-school expense per-student.²⁶³ For students whose household income is between 185% and 250% of the federal poverty level, scholarships must be 75% of costs and fees or public school expenses

²⁵³ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/20; 35 Ill. Comp. Ann. 40/35.

²⁵⁴ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/35.

²⁵⁵ See 35 Ill. Comp. Ann. 40/40.

²⁵⁶ *Id.*

²⁵⁷ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/40

²⁵⁸ *Id.*

²⁵⁹ See 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/40. A focus district is a school district which has a school that is either a school with one or more subgroups which perform at or below the state average for the lowest 10% of students in that subgroup or a school with an average graduation rate of less than 60% that has not been identified for priority. See 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/5.

²⁶⁰ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/40.

²⁶¹ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/40.

²⁶² *Id.*

²⁶³ *Id.*

per-student.²⁶⁴ For students whose household income is greater than 250% the federal poverty level, scholarships must be 50% of the costs or public school expenses per-student.²⁶⁵

Qualified schools are subject to a variety of regulations.²⁶⁶ Schools are required to be accountable to custodians of students by, at a minimum, providing custodians with a written explanation of their student’s progress.²⁶⁷ Qualified schools are also required to administer assessments “in the same manner in which they are administered at public schools”.²⁶⁸ Participating schools are required to report individual student scores to the custodians of students.²⁶⁹ Additionally, score data must be provided to an “independent research organization” set up under the program.²⁷⁰ In order to participate in the program a private school must be “recognized” by the state board.²⁷¹ However, qualified schools do not need to be accredited by the state board or any other organization.²⁷²

The Illinois contains a provision that provides for the automatic repeal of the program on January 1, 2024.²⁷³

II. Montana (2015)

²⁶⁴ *Id.*

²⁶⁵ *Id.*

²⁶⁶ *See e.g.* 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/50.

²⁶⁷ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/50.

²⁶⁸ *Id.*

²⁶⁹ *Id.*

²⁷⁰ *Id.*

²⁷¹ 35 Ill. Comp. 40/5; 105 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 5/2-3.25o (giving the state board the power to register and recognize non-public schools); Ill. Admin. Code tit. 23, § 425.30 (stating the process and requirements for non-public school registration and recognition by the board).

²⁷² *Id.*

²⁷³ 35 Ill. Comp. Stat. Ann. 40/65.

The Montana program²⁷⁴ is called the “Tax Credit for Qualified Education Contributions”.²⁷⁵ The program was adopted in 2015.²⁷⁶ The program’s tax credit is valued at 100% of donation value.²⁷⁷ Both businesses and individual taxpayers may claim the credit.²⁷⁸ The individual cap on credits is \$150.²⁷⁹ The initial total cap on credits is \$3,000,000.²⁸⁰ However, if the program cap is reached in a given year, then the program cap is required to be increased by 10% in the succeeding tax year.²⁸¹ Although the program prohibits taxpayers from claiming a credit and a charitable deduction for state tax purposes, there is no explicit prohibition against claiming a state credit and federal deduction.²⁸² The identity of taxpayers who claim a credit under the program is explicitly required to be kept confidential by a provision in the statute.²⁸³

Taxpayers may claim a program tax credit for two different types of donation. Credits are available on donations to private schools under the “qualified education tax credit for contributions to student scholarship organizations”, and on donations to a public-school under the “credit for providing supplemental funding to Public Schools- innovative educational program”.²⁸⁴ If making a donation to an “innovative educational program” taxpayers have the power to direct their donation to a specific “geographic region”²⁸⁵ or “large district”.²⁸⁶ If a taxpayer specifies that the

²⁷⁴ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3101 to -3114.

²⁷⁵ *Id.*

²⁷⁶ MT LEGIS 457 (2015), 2015 Montana Laws Ch. 457 (S.B. 410).

²⁷⁷ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3110.

²⁷⁸ *Id.*

²⁷⁹ *Id.*

²⁸⁰ *Id.*

²⁸¹ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3110.

²⁸² Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3110. According to Big Sky Scholarships, currently the only SGO in Montana, the tax credit can be claimed with the federal tax deduction.

²⁸³ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3113.

²⁸⁴ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3110. *See also* Mont. Code Ann. § 20-9-904.

²⁸⁵ Geographic regions are groupings of counties. A geographic region contains all of the area within its composite counties, except for the areas occupied by “large districts”. *See* Mont. Code Ann. § 20-9-903.

²⁸⁶ Mont. Code Ann. 15-30-3110. A “large district” is a district that is one of the seven largest districts in the state. As of the 2017 legislative session, Billings, Butte, Bozeman, Great Falls, Helena, Kalipsell, and Missoula were listed as large districts. *See* Mont. Code Ann. § 20-9-903.

donation is to be used in a “geographic region” then it may not be used in a large district and vice versa.²⁸⁷

To be eligible, a student must be a Montana resident who is 5 years old by September 10 of the year for which they will receive the scholarship.²⁸⁸ Additionally, eligible students must not have reached 19 years of age.²⁸⁹ Scholarship values may not exceed 50% of the per-pupil average of total public-school expenditures.²⁹⁰ Additionally, an SGOs average scholarship value may not exceed 30% of the per-pupil average of total public-school expenditures.²⁹¹ Scholarships are not required to cover the full cost of attendance at a school.²⁹²

SGOs are given the label “student scholarship organization”.²⁹³ SGOs are required to spend at least 90% of donations on scholarship grants.²⁹⁴ Like all other programs, SGOs are required to be exempt from federal income taxation under section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code.²⁹⁵ Thus, SGOs are effectively prohibited from providing scholarships to schools with racially discriminatory policies.²⁹⁶ SGOs may not limit scholarships to only one school or one particular type of school.²⁹⁷ SGOs are subject to other minor regulations including a requirement that SGOs make annual reports to the Montana Department of Revenue.²⁹⁸ Furthermore, SGOs are subject to other reporting requirements, including the requirement that SGOs make qualified school test

²⁸⁷ *Id.*

²⁸⁸ Mont. Code. Ann. § 15-30-3102.

²⁸⁹ *Id.*

²⁹⁰ Mont. Code. Ann. § 15-30-3103.

²⁹¹ *Id.*

²⁹² *Id.*

²⁹³ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3102.

²⁹⁴ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3102.

²⁹⁵ *Id.*

²⁹⁶ *Supra* n. 178.

²⁹⁷ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3103.

²⁹⁸ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3103.

performance information available to the public by posting the information on a publicly accessible website.

Qualified schools must administer “a nationally recognized standardized assessment test or criterion referenced test” and to make the results available to a participating student’s parents or legal guardian.²⁹⁹ Furthermore, aggregate test scores for 8th grade and 11th grade participating students must be made available to the public either through a privately owned publicly accessible website or through the office of public instruction’s website.³⁰⁰ Qualified schools are required to be accredited, to have applied for accreditation, or have been previously accredited by a state, regional, or national accreditation organization.³⁰¹ However, a qualified school may participate if it is non-accredited and not seeking accreditation, so long as the school informs the child’s legal guardian in writing at the time of enrollment.³⁰²

The most notable regulation concerning qualified schools is the prohibition against religiously affiliated private schools.³⁰³ Specifically, qualified schools may not be owned in whole or in part by a “church, religious sect or denomination”.³⁰⁴ Furthermore, qualified schools cannot be owned an individual who is employed by an institution that is wholly or partially owned by a church, religious sect, or denomination.³⁰⁵ This regulation is not included in the statutory law governing the program. Instead, the regulation is found in an administrative rule that was enacted

²⁹⁹ Mont. Code. Ann. § 15-30-3102.

³⁰⁰ Mont. Code. Ann. § 15-30-3102.

³⁰¹ Mont. Code. Ann. § 15-30-3102.

³⁰² *Id.*

³⁰³ Admin. R. Mont. 42.4.802.

³⁰⁴ Admin. R. Mont. 42.4.802.

³⁰⁵ Admin. R. Mont. 42.4.802.

pursuant to the statutory provision allowing for regulations to be imposed through agency rulemaking.³⁰⁶

The regulation was adopted in 2015, before to the first school year where scholarships would be available. The Department of Revenue regulation was made ineffective in March of that year when a district judge issued a preliminary injunction against enforcement of the regulation after it was challenged by students who claimed that if not for the regulation they would have attended private school.³⁰⁷ In May 2017 the district court granted the challengers' motion for summary judgment and permanently enjoined the program.³⁰⁸ There, the court reasoned that the program was not connotational because the Montana constitution bans aiding religious schools through appropriations, but is silent on use of tax credits.³⁰⁹ The State has appealed the case to the Montana Supreme Court and it is scheduled to be heard in early 2018.

The Montana program automatically terminates on December 31, 2023.³¹⁰

III. Nevada (2015)

The Nevada program³¹¹ is called “Nevada Educational Choice Scholarship Program”.³¹² The program was enacted during the 2015 legislative session.³¹³ The value of the credit is

³⁰⁶ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3114.

³⁰⁷ http://billingsgazette.com/news/government-and-politics/judge-school-choice-money-can-help-private-school-students/article_dc17886a-9eb3-5511-b2b8-5ca3694dd457.html

³⁰⁸ Kendra ESPINOZA, Jeri Ellen Anderson and Jaime Schefer, Plaintiffs and Appellees, v. MONTANA DEPARTMENT OF REVENUE and Mike Kadas, in his official capacity as Director of the Montana Department of Revenue, Defendants and Appellants., 2017 WL 5894960 (Mont

³⁰⁹ Espinoza (TRIAL COURT ORDER)(“the term ‘appropriation’ used in Article V, Section 11(5) and in Article X, Section 6(1) does not encompass tax credits.”)

³¹⁰ Mont. Code Ann. § 15-30-3102.

³¹¹ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.199 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. §§ 388D.250 to .280 (West).

³¹² Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.250 (West).

³¹³ EDUCATION—DONATION—SCHOLARSHIPS, 2015 Nevada Laws Ch. 22 (A.B. 165).

effectively 100% the value of the donation.³¹⁴ Only certain businesses are allowed to claim the program's credits.³¹⁵ The program contains multiple provisions regarding cap on total tax credits.³¹⁶ Initially, the program's total cap was \$5,000,000 for the 2015-16 fiscal year and \$5,500,000 for the 2016-17 fiscal year.³¹⁷ In each subsequent year, total available credits must be increased by 10%.³¹⁸ Additionally, for the 2017-18 fiscal year, an additional \$20,000,000 in credits was made available.³¹⁹ These additional credits were made available after state lawmakers were unable to pass legislation to establish an Educational Savings Account (ESA) program.³²⁰ Thus, for the 2017-18 fiscal year a total of 26,050,000 in credits were available under the program.³²¹ Information on taxpayers who claim program tax credits appears to be required to be kept confidential under Nevada law.³²²

Eligible students must be members of households whose household income must be less than 300% of the federal poverty level.³²³ Although students are not explicitly required to be residents of Nevada, scholarships can only be applied toward tuition at schools within the state.³²⁴

³¹⁴ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West)(providing that the total amount of the credit must “not exceed the amount of the donation”).

³¹⁵ Specifically, businesses that are required to pay payroll tax or Nevada's business tax. *See* Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 362A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.119 (West).

³¹⁶ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.119 (West).

³¹⁷ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.119 (West).

³¹⁸ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.119 (West).

³¹⁹ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.119 (West).

³²⁰ <https://www.reviewjournal.com/news/education/nevada-scholarship-program-benefits-from-political-deadlock-over-esas/>

³²¹ *See* http://www.doe.nv.gov/Private_Schools/Nevada_Choice_Scholarship_Program/.

³²² Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 360.255 (West).

³²³ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³²⁴ Nev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

Scholarship values are initially limited to \$7,755.³²⁵ However, maximum value is required to be annually adjusted in reference to the percentage increase in the Consumer Price Index for the preceding calendar year.³²⁶ The scholarships are not required to cover the full cost of attendance.³²⁷

An SGO is called a “scholarship organization” under the program.³²⁸ SGOs are prohibited from spending more than 5% of donations on administrative expenses.³²⁹ Additionally, SGOs are required to make limited annual reports to the Department of Education.³³⁰ Although SGOs are prohibited from limiting scholarships to one school, there is no prohibition against limiting scholarships to a particular type of school.³³¹ The statutes contain no provisions explicitly prohibiting discrimination.³³² However, like other programs, SGOs are required to maintain 501(c)(3) nonprofit status, which effectively prohibits SGOs from distributing funds to schools with racially discriminatory policies.³³³

SGOs are subject to a few regulations limiting their decision making over scholarship distributions.³³⁴ For example, SGOs are required to prioritize students who have previously received scholarships and their siblings.³³⁵ Otherwise, SGOs are required to issue grants on first come first serve basis. Regulatory rules determine SGO decision making when two pupils apply on the same day and the SGO only has enough funds to provide one with a scholarship.³³⁶

³²⁵ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³²⁶ *Id.*

³²⁷ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³²⁸ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.260 (West).

³²⁹ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³³⁰ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.280 (West).

³³¹ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³³² *See* Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363A.139 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 363B.199 (West); Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. §§ 388D.250 to .280 (West).

³³³ *Supra* n. 178.

³³⁴ *See e.g.* Nev. Admin. Code 385.6043.

³³⁵ Nev. Admin. Code 385.043.

³³⁶ Nev. Admin. Code 385.043.

However, it is not exactly clear what effect these rules have, since SGOs are not required to grant a scholarship to a pupil solely because their application is complete.³³⁷

Qualified schools are required to maintain a record of academic progress for all participating students enrolled at that school.³³⁸ Additionally, these records must be maintained in such a manner so that information may be aggregated and reported for all participating students, “if reporting is required by the regulations of the Department of Education” that may be prescribed under the program.³³⁹ It appears that the Department of Education has enacted regulations requiring some type of aggregate reporting.³⁴⁰

IV. South Dakota (2016)

The South Dakota program³⁴¹ is called the “Partners in Education Tax Credit Program”.³⁴² The program was adopted during the 2016 legislative session.³⁴³ The program’s tax credit can be claimed by businesses that are liable to pay the insurance company premium and annuity tax.³⁴⁴ The value of the program’s tax credit is equal to 80% of donation value.³⁴⁵ The program’s total cap on credits is \$2,000,000.³⁴⁶ The program does not specify an individual cap on credits.³⁴⁷ Participating taxpayers and their donation amounts are kept confidential by law. However,

³³⁷ *Id.*

³³⁸ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³³⁹ Nev. Rev. Stat. Ann. § 388D.270 (West).

³⁴⁰ Nev. Admin. Code § 385.6065; http://www.doe.nv.gov/Private_Schools/Nevada_Choice_Scholarship_Program/.

³⁴¹ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1 to -65-12.

³⁴² S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-2.

³⁴³ SD LEGIS 102 (2016), 2016 South Dakota Laws Ch. 102 (SB 159).

³⁴⁴ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-2.

³⁴⁵ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-2.

³⁴⁶ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-3.

³⁴⁷ *Id.*

participating taxpayers have voluntarily released information in a report made by the program's main political advocate Partners in Education.³⁴⁸

To be eligible, a student must be a member of a household whose total income did not exceed 150% of the maximum income that qualifies a student to receive free or reduced-price lunches.³⁴⁹ Once a student meets the initial income eligibility requirement, the student is deemed eligible for three years regardless of household income, provided that sufficient funding is available.³⁵⁰ Additionally, an eligible student retains eligibility after entering high school regardless of household income, provided sufficient funding is available.³⁵¹ Furthermore, after a student is initially deemed eligible, the student continues to be eligible provided that the student's household income does not exceed 200% of the maximum income that qualifies a student to receive free or reduced price lunches.³⁵²

There is also a type of prior public-school enrollment requirement for student eligibility.³⁵³ Students must have either received a scholarship under the program in the preceding semester or attended a public-school the preceding semester.³⁵⁴ However, if a student is starting at a school in South Dakota for the first time, there is no prior public school enrollment requirement.³⁵⁵ Furthermore, for students entering kindergarten, first grade, or ninth grade, there is no prior public school enrollment requirement.³⁵⁶ Like the Kansas program, the language in the South Dakota

³⁴⁸ <http://sdlegislature.gov/docs/interim/2017/documents/goa7-24-17SouthDakotaPartnersInEducationTaxCreditScholarshipProgramJune302017.pdf>

³⁴⁹ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁵⁰ *Id.*

³⁵¹ *Id.*

³⁵² *Id.*

³⁵³ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁵⁴ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁵⁵ *Id.*

³⁵⁶ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

statutes may be imprecise, as the provision requires only that a student must have “attended a public school the preceding semester”, but otherwise does not specify a minimum length of time.³⁵⁷

The maximum value of scholarships available under the program is not specified.³⁵⁸ However, the average value of scholarships awarded by an SGO may not exceed 82.5% of the state’s share of the “per student equivalent”.³⁵⁹ Scholarships are not required to cover the full cost of attendance at a qualified school.³⁶⁰

The South Dakota program calls SGOs “scholarship granting organization”.³⁶¹ SGOs are required to be a nonprofit organization under section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code.³⁶² Thus, SGOs are effectively prohibited from distributing funds to schools with racially discriminatory policies.³⁶³ SGOs must spend at least 90% of donations on scholarships.³⁶⁴ The program requires SGOs to make limited annual reports to the South Dakota Division of Revenue.³⁶⁵

Qualified schools must be accredited by the South Dakota Department of Education.³⁶⁶ There are very few regulations placed on qualified schools.³⁶⁷ Additionally, a provision in the program’s statutes explains that the program does not expand the regulatory authority of state or allow the state’s officers to impose additional regulations on nonpublic schools.³⁶⁸

³⁵⁷ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁵⁸ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁵⁹ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1. *See also* S.D. Codified Laws § 13-13-10.1 (defining the state’s share of the per student equivalent).

³⁶⁰ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁶¹ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁶² S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-4.

³⁶³ *Supra* n. 178.

³⁶⁴ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-4.

³⁶⁵ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-4.

³⁶⁶ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-1.

³⁶⁷ *Id.*

³⁶⁸ S.D. Codified Laws § 13-65-12.

The governor of South Dakota sought an advisory opinion from the state's supreme court on the issue of whether the program was constitutional.³⁶⁹ The court held that it would be unconstitutional for the court to issue an advisory opinion on the program's constitutionality.³⁷⁰

³⁶⁹ *In re Dugaard*, 884 N.W.2d 163, 167 (S.D. 2016).

³⁷⁰ *Id.*